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SOCIAL INCLUSION IN 15-MINUTE CITY URBAN POLICY: THE CASE OF MILAN

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Abstract

The 15-minute city concept, which is becoming more popular in urban planning post-Covid-19, aims to make cities more livable and sustainable by ensuring that all necessary services and amenities are within a 15-minute walk or bike ride from home. While this policy may have numerous advantages, like minimizing car dependency, promoting physical activity, and improving the quality of life for urban residents, there is a chance that it may inadvertently exclude some groups from using these services, especially those who are already marginalized or disadvantaged. This thesis explores the social inclusion aspect of the 15-minute city urban policy, using Milan as a case study. Also, the study aims to identify whether the 15-minute city policy widens the gap between the rich and the poor and whether it adequately addresses the needs of vulnerable populations, such as the elderly and disabled. In order to evaluate the potential advantages and disadvantages of the policy, a literature analysis was conducted first with an emphasis on its social sustainability dimension. The research continued with a case study in Milan, gathering information regarding the policy implementation mostly from documents published on the municipality's official website and neighborhood information from the municipality's geoportal website and the Milan census document. The study examines whether the characteristics of the neighborhood and the type of intervention being implemented as part of the 15-minute city policy aligns with the requirements of the residents in that neighborhood. The study also sought to determine the level of social inclusion by identifying where the problems persist and where the solutions are being implemented by comparing the neighborhoods where the policy is being implemented with vulnerable neighborhoods in Milan. The results indicate that the bottom-up approach of the policy can result in exclusionary outcomes because some neighborhoods might not be aware of or able to respond to the call for initiatives due to several barriers. In order to ensure that the policy is beneficial to the entire community, the study suggests taking into account the needs of all groups in different neighborhoods when implementing the policy.

Key words: 15-minute city, Sustainable urban policy, social inclusion.

Abstract in lingua italiana

Il concetto di città dei 15 minuti, che sta diventando sempre più popolare nella pianificazione urbana post-Covid-19, mira a rendere le città più vivibili e sostenibili assicurando che tutti i servizi e le attrezzature necessarie siano raggiungibili a piedi o in bicicletta entro 15 minuti da casa. Sebbene questa politica possa avere numerosi vantaggi, come la riduzione della dipendenza dall'auto, la promozione dell'attività fisica e il miglioramento della qualità della vita dei residenti urbani, esiste il rischio che possa escludere involontariamente alcuni gruppi dall'utilizzo di questi servizi, specialmente coloro che sono già emarginati o svantaggiati. Questa tesi esplora l'aspetto dell'inclusione sociale della politica urbana delle città dei 15 minuti, utilizzando Milano come caso di studio. Lo studio mira anche a identificare se la politica delle città dei 15 minuti allarga il divario tra ricchi e poveri e se affronta adeguatamente le esigenze delle popolazioni vulnerabili, come gli anziani e i disabili. Per valutare i potenziali vantaggi e svantaggi della politica, è stata condotta un'analisi della letteratura, con un'attenzione particolare alla sua dimensione di sostenibilità sociale. La ricerca è proseguita con uno studio di caso a Milano, raccogliendo informazioni sulla implementazione della politica principalmente da documenti pubblicati sul sito web ufficiale del comune e informazioni sul quartiere dal geoportale e dal censimento di Milano. Lo studio esamina se le caratteristiche del quartiere e il tipo di intervento che viene implementato come parte della politica delle città dei 15 minuti corrispondono alle esigenze dei residenti in quel quartiere. Lo studio ha anche cercato di determinare il livello di inclusione sociale identificando dove persistono i problemi e dove vengono implementate le soluzioni, confrontando i quartieri in cui viene implementata la politica con i quartieri vulnerabili di Milano. I risultati indicano che l'approccio dal basso della politica può portare a esiti di esclusione perché alcuni quartieri potrebbero non essere a conoscenza o in grado di rispondere alla chiamata per le iniziative a causa di diversi ostacoli. Per garantire che la politica sia benefica per l'intera comunità, lo studio suggerisce di tenere conto delle esigenze di tutti i gruppi nei diversi quartieri durante l'implementazione della politica.

Parole chiave: città dei 15 minuti, politica urbana sostenibile, inclusione sociale.

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Introduction

According to the world bank, cities are home to more than half of the world's population - 56%, or 4.4 billion people. This tendency is predicted to continue, by 2050, approximately 7 out of 10 people worldwide are expected to live in cities (World Bank, 2018). The rapid and massive size of urbanization raises challenges such as affordable housing, pollution, efficient infrastructure and transportation systems, basic and public services, poverty, employment availability, and social equality. In order to address these challenges and combat climate change and manage the expected exponential urbanization around the globe, Sustainable urban development has become a major theme in urban planning for the last two decades. World organizations make tremendous efforts to create targets and agendas for the coming decades, such as the UN-Habitat New Urban Agenda 2030 in the global context and the European Green Deal 2050 in the European context, etc.

When the COVID-19 Pandemic hit the globe in the early months of 2020, it brought the cities to a complete halt for several months. It forced everyone to fundamentally reevaluate their way of life as a result of the Pandemic. Carlos Moreno came up with a possible solution: the so-called "15-minute city". His concept is based on the idea that everyone's needs can be met during a 15-minute trip that includes walking and cycling. The 15-minute city concept acquired considerable recognition after C40 cities, an international group of mayors from major cities, began to promote it as an "alternative paradigm of urban development" (Global mayors COVID-19 recovery task force, 2020). The concept has received media attention and support from mayors of several cities. A number of cities, including Milan, Paris, New York, Singapore, and others, have declared that they will adopt the concept as a key plan of action for their post-pandemic recovery.

The main objective of implementing this policy in various cities is to decrease car usage and, consequently, CO2 emissions. Many cities around the world have started implementing initiatives as part of this policy, measures such as constructing cycle lanes and enforcing speed limits have been put into place in numerous cities. These efforts primarily focus on reducing CO2 emissions and improving air quality, giving more attention to the environmental aspect of sustainability. However, it is important to note that the social side of sustainability is often overlooked. Several experts concerns that the

15-minute city policy may lead to other problems, such as rising housing costs and segregation (Glaeser, 2021., Zivarts, 2021) express. Since the 15-minute city policy is a decentralized urban planning concept in which each local neighborhood comprises all the fundamental social functions for living and working, it is crucial to ensure that all neighborhoods receive high-quality amenities to prevent gentrification. According to Manchester University sociology professor Elisa Pieri, if 15-minute cities do not reach this equilibrium, impoverished neighborhoods may have fewer resources, such as fewer and lower-quality teachers and medical professionals. The result could enhance discrimination, injustice, and territorial stigma.

During the pandemic, Cities have realized the value of having quick access to urban services and how much our neighborhoods lack urban amenities at a local level. Many cities are implementing the 15-minute city or other similar techniques as a strategy to recover from the pandemic, build back the cities better, and make them resilient. The 15-minute city strategy provides a mechanism to build on successful reforms to strengthen local economies and provide long-lasting benefits for equity, health, and the environment. Therefore, there is a necessity to rethink the design of our cities with a focus on neighborhoods and seriously consider the strategies and guidelines provided in the vision for the “15-minute” city.

This thesis focuses on the social inclusion aspect of the 15-minute city urban policy in Milan. To ensure that the 15-minute city policy is sustainable, it is crucial to consider the social inclusion aspect of this policy. Failing to do so can result in the exclusion of vulnerable populations, such as low-income households, elderly people, and those with disabilities. This exclusion can also lead to increased social segregation, as wealthier residents will live in areas with better access to amenities and services, while marginalized communities are left behind. Furthermore, this can also limit economic opportunities for disadvantaged populations, as they may not have access to job opportunities or participate fully in the local economy. Hence, it is imperative to prioritize social inclusion in the implementation of the 15-minute city policy to ensure that all members of the community have equal access to the benefits of the policy. Therefore, the objective of the thesis is to focus on the level of social inclusion of the policy by examining whether it has widened the gap between the rich and the poor and whether it has taken into account the needs of vulnerable populations such as the elderly and disabled. Also, through a case study of Milan, the research examines the social inclusion

aspect of the 15-minute city urban policy, aiming to identify the potential challenges and opportunities for promoting equity and inclusion in urban planning.

The findings of this study will provide valuable insights of the approach and strategy Milan uses to implement the policy, and the extent to which Milan's 15-minute city policy is socially inclusive and provide insights into how to improve the policy to ensure that it benefits all members of society.

Structure of the thesis

This thesis is structured in seven chapters. The first chapter provides a background and evolution of the 15-minute city concept, as well as the framework of the 15-minute city policy. The second chapter contains a literature review that critically analyzes existing literature on the policy, including both positive and negative impacts. The third chapter identifies research questions based on the gaps found in the literature review. The fourth chapter describes the methodology used to collect data regarding the policy in Milan, including information on where the policy is implemented and how vulnerable neighborhoods were identified. It also details the analysis methods used to map and compare the policy approach to gain insights. The fifth chapter introduces the 15-minute city case in Milan, explaining the strategy and different interventions implemented. The sixth chapter presents the results and findings, which includes an overview of all the interventions being implemented in Milan as part of the 15-minute city policy, a list of vulnerable neighborhoods, and the findings of vulnerable neighborhoods without intervention. The final chapter, the conclusion, summarizes the research findings, discusses implications for urban planning and policy in Milan and beyond, and identifies limitations of the study and future research directions.

1 15-minute city urban policy

In this chapter, an analytical definition of the 15-minute city urban policy will be provided. This will involve exploring the key principles and goals of the policy, as well as its origins and evolution over time. Additionally, the chapter will examine the pillars of this policy in detail and explain the framework of the 15-minute city policy.

Since the COVID-19 outbreak plans that promote mixed-use, vibrant neighborhoods with close access to services and opportunities have gained increased popularity in cities around the world. The 15-minute city is one of these ideas that has gained widespread attention and has been adopted and interpreted in numerous different locations and circumstances. According to the "15-minute city" concept, cities should be planned or replanned so that daily requirements like employment, home, food, education, healthcare, parks, and so on are accessible on foot or by bicycle within a 15-minute commute. The principal proponent of the idea has been identified as Carlos Moreno. He developed the idea in 2016 (Moreno, 2020), but it became well-known during the political campaign of the current mayor of Paris. Mayor Anne Hidalgo's reelection campaign in 2019 centered on solving the concerns of climate change and improving the liveability of Parisians. This emerging concept is now being implemented in major European cities like Barcelona and Paris, and it is gaining popularity as a potent strategy for promoting changes toward urban sustainability.

The idea of a 15-minute City is not radically new (Pozoukidou & Chatziyiannaki, 2021). It is derived from the previously existing concept of urban walkability and proximity. Neighborhood units, iso-benefit urbanism, and whole communities are a few examples that have focused on the same idea of walkability and proximity. Clarence Perry first proposed the idea of neighborhood units with the goal of building communities where everyone could live close to essential amenities like supermarkets, parks, and schools without having to go far (Casellia, Carrab, Rossetta, Zazzia, 2021). In order to address the immediate challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic as well as to address the climate breakdown in cities, the mayors of the C40 cities developed a 'Green and just recovery' program (Global mayors COVID-19 recovery task force, 2020). The C40 network's agenda for a "Green and Just Recovery" includes the 15-minute city urban design policy. The

concept of a 15-minute city policy is expressly included in the Agenda for a Green and Just Recovery as a framework for rebounding and affirming cities' commitment to the 'Global Green New Deal'. The Global Green New Deal places inclusive climate action at the center of urban decision-making with a focus on protecting the environment, boosting the economy, and creating a more equitable future by reducing emissions from the industries most responsible for the climate crisis to keep global warming below the 1.5C goal of the Paris Agreement (Global mayors COVID-19 recovery task force, 2020). Therefore, the 15-minute city policy is part of the program for a 'green and just recovery', which has a vision for a rapid, equitable recovery from the COVID-19 crisis and is founded on the principles of a global green new deal to bring about transformative benefits for global health, economy, and emission reduction.

THE 15-MINUTE PARIS

Figure 1: The 15-minute city illustration (Moreno, et. al., 2021)

1.1 The 15-minute city framework

The 15-Minute City is based on the idea of "chrono-urbanism," which holds that the quality of urban living is inversely related to the time spent in transit, especially when using a car. According to Moreno's "15-minute" notion, city dwellers will be able to live more comfortably in areas where they can successfully carry out the six key social duties required to maintain a respectable urban lifestyle. Living, working, commerce, healthcare, education, and amusement are among them. To attain those functions (Moreno et al., 2021) propose the '15-minute city framework' consisting of 4 dimensions (Figure 2) in the order:

- Building Density,
- Proximity.
- Diversity.
- Digitalization.

Figure 2: Moreno's 15-minute city framework's prescriptive elements (Moreno et. Al., 2021)

1. **Building density:** According to Moreno, density is an important consideration when planning cities because it directly affects travel and diversity. Density is typically thought of in terms of extremely high-density buildings. But the 15-Min City concept is thought of in terms of people per square kilometer. In other words, it is advised that when designing a sustainable city, it is critical to take into account

the ideal population that a particular location can support without straining the ability of the city to provide services and consume resources. The creation of ultra-high-rise buildings and offices was the focus of earlier planning models, but this led to problems such as increased resource overconsumption and an overreliance on fossil fuel energy to power buildings, which ultimately resulted in an increase in the number of automobiles motivated by centralized planning ideologies. So, the emphasis in the 15-minute city concept is on the ideal density that, in the end, enables sustainability goals to be attained on the economic, social, and environmental frontiers (Moreno et. Al., 2021).

(Salingaros, 2006) emphasizes that with the right density, it is possible to efficiently manage the space that is available so that residents may access all of their needs without having to use time- and energy-consuming cars. Additionally, he asserted that an ideal density enables the development of regional solutions for issues like energy production, food supply, and multiple uses of available space, where, for instance, school playgrounds may double as parks. The benefits of density were further recognized by the author (Moreno, et al.,2021) as follows:

-Density must also provide for the spatial and social equity of various neighborhoods, groups, and economic and social backgrounds. Via an equitable service allocation, it will specifically favor the underprivileged.

-Density will enable cities to deliver services at a lower cost, generating great value for governments and investors. As a result, density, when combined with closeness, diversity, and digitalization, is a major factor in social sustainability.

- 2. Proximity:** Proximity is said to be both spatial and temporal. In other words, people of a specific community can easily get basic services inside the 15-minute quickly accessible radial nodes. This aspect is crucial for helping cities reduce the amount of time lost in commuting as well as the negative effects such activity has on the economy and the environment. This aids in identifying social factors affecting city dwellers, particularly in an effort to foster social contact (Jacobs, J. 2020). According to Moreno (2021), this aspect is crucial since it enables residents to move quickly between their homes, places of employment, commercial districts, educational institutions, healthcare facilities, and other basic institutions. Finally,

because of the planning model's support for multimodal usage of fundamental infrastructure, citizens can benefit from enhanced service delivery in both commercial and public organizations. (Moreno, 2021) also cites Paris as an example, where Mayor Hidalgo has welcomed this novel idea, and it has been customary to convert school playgrounds into public parks that are open to the public after school. With this and other instances, it becomes clear why it is crucial to pursue the proximity dimension since it enables local inhabitants to make the most of their public spaces, green areas, and other public infrastructures. Also, it enables people to get the most out of their existing resources, such as their cultural history, for social, economic, and environmental advantages.

This concept is crucial because it enables the visualization of a city from a different angle, one that is better suited to the human scale and flexible to the needs of its inhabitants. It is further asserted that the notion of proximity used in this context is an improvement on that found in the theories of chrono-urbanism, chronotropy, and topophilia, which couple the geographical and temporal dimensions.

3. **Diversity:** Diversity has two aspects in the context of the aforementioned framework and the development of the 15-Minute City concept: (i) the requirement for mixed-use neighborhoods, which are essential in supplying a wholesome mixture of residential, commercial, and entertainment components; and (ii) diversity in people and culture (Moreno et al., 2021).

Having mixed-use communities is crucial in preserving economically dynamic urban fabrics, assuring sufficient housing for all urban people, fostering inclusivity, and supporting sustainable practices. In the pursuit of a 15-Minute City model, the adoption of mixed-use communities is vital in ensuring that an optimal density and proximity of essential amenities are reached, while also providing for the development of walking streets and bicycle lanes. With this strategy, residents are guaranteed access to basic necessities close to where they live, which eliminates the need for them to travel. This aspect would help to ensure that the sacredness of already existing public spaces is maintained and safeguarded as well as, whenever possible, that possibilities to create new public spaces are appreciated, as was suggested by (Whyte W.H et al., 2009)

A city's multiculturalism has positive effects on its economy since residents will enjoy a wide range of goods including cultural items and local history. This would also create a more appealing urban environment for tourists, supporting tourism and other associated industries that are crucial for generating new business and boosting economic vitality, which in turn creates more employment prospects (Moreno et al.,2021). This dimension needs to be used throughout a city at various scales in order to maximize those advantages. Not just on an urban size within a 15-minute radius, but also on smaller scales, including at the building level.

- 4. Digitalization-** This dimension is crucial to the modified 15-Minute City concept, particularly in ensuring that the three other dimensions are actually realized. It might be argued that the 15-Minute City concept was somewhat inspired by the Smart City concept because this dimension, in particular, strongly correlates with it. For instance, exactly like in Moreno's suggested model, the Smart City concept encourages elements like diversity, resident participation, and real-time service delivery across a variety of platforms, including digital. More service availabilities in 15-minute cities would lessen the need for commuting because some services, such as online shopping and cashless transactions, may be provided from the convenience of homes or offices. They could be combined with blockchain-based smart contracts to reduce security issues, particularly with reference to virtual payments. Digitalization has made it feasible for people to connect online and work from home, especially during this time of the COVID-19 pandemic. This has also helped to reduce social contact and the necessity for travel from homes to offices and other work locations (Moreno et al., 2021) Deploying digital solutions would also significantly contribute to meeting or even exceeding the goals of the 15-minute city, especially in terms of ensuring that cities are more resilient to issues like climate change through lowering emissions, connected to a decrease in automobile use (Chel et al., 2020). Through innovations like iBike, which enable people to share bikes in cities and encourage them to reduce the use of personal cars, digitalization is also increasingly effective at creating jobs. Since digitalization has been viewed as a transversal element that cuts across fields, it is anticipated that it will also be crucial to the successful implementation of the other three dimensions. All of those are anticipated to benefit greatly from its arrival.

2 Literature review

This chapter discusses the theoretical outlines that describe the current state of literature. The literature review chapter of this thesis is structured around various subheadings that examine the development of the policy, and its potential positive and negative impacts it produces in an urban context. The first section focuses on the social, health, environmental, and economical benefits of this policy. The analysis of multi-dimensional perspectives of urban policy allows for a comprehensive understanding of the impacts and potential trade-offs of the policy. In a report by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2016), it was emphasized that policies must be evaluated with a holistic approach that takes into account their potential social, economic, and environmental impacts. This approach is important for ensuring that policies contribute to sustainable development goals. The second section analyzes the benefits of walkability and its relationship to affordability of housing and the following section analyzes the social cohesion and social capital in walkable neighborhoods. The purpose of this analysis is to investigate the potential advantages and disadvantages of neighborhoods that are walkable. In particular, the relationship between walkability and social capital given that it encourages social interaction and a sense of belonging, as well as the relationship between walkability and housing affordability to determine whether walkability will raise housing prices and lead to gentrification.

The fourth section analyzes the potential beneficiaries of the 15-minute city policy. A beneficiary analysis can help identify the groups of residents who are likely to be impacted by the policy, and how they may benefit or be disadvantaged by the policy. This analysis can help evaluate the policy's effectiveness and identify potential challenges and trade-offs. The fifth section explores the current exclusion of vulnerable people in the urban context. The goal of this analysis is to comprehend the current urban exclusionary elements that vulnerable people face in an urban context and to determine whether the 15-minute city policy can address this issue.

Furthermore, in the following section, an analysis was conducted on existing methods to evaluate the accessibility of the nearby services to neighborhood residents. This is to gain an understanding of how the accessibility index is calculated across various cities. It has

been observed that many methods tend to focus on average speed, which can be problematic because they do not account for the specific needs and limitations of certain population groups, such as the elderly and disabled. As a result, it is possible that these groups may not be able to access services within the same time frame as others, leading to disparities in access and potentially impacting their quality of life. The seventh section provides a list of cities that have already implemented and are implementing similar strategies. This is to gain valuable insights on how different cities are approaching the policy and the various strategies they use to implement it. The final section evaluates the impact of similar strategies implemented in other cities through impact evaluation reports. Examining the experiences of other cities that have implemented similar policies, we can learn from their successes and challenges and better understand the potential outcomes of this policy. The ultimate goal is to identify any gaps in the literature that may exist and, consequently, to determine how this thesis fits into the larger existing context.

2.1 Positive impacts of the 15-minute city concept: social, health, environmental, and economic

Below are the diverse impacts of the 15-minute city policy in terms of social, health, environment and economy. This information is taken from various research papers and are listed below.

2.1.1 Social impact

Since the 15-minute city is a "people-centered model," social impact is one of the most crucial factors. Urban regeneration enhances neighborhood walkability and cyclability enhances social cohesiveness and a sense of place placemaking, where neighbors get to know one another, feeling like they are a part of the community and engaged with it. By using natural surveillance, mixed users, and activities that keep public areas active, crime is decreased, and the feeling of security is improved (Allam et al., 2022). The "15-minute city" concept aims to reclaim time lost to traffic jams and commutes so that it can be used for family time, socializing with friends, leisure time, and other activities that enhance wellness (Moreno et al., 2021).

2.1.2 Cohesion and social capital benefits

A number of positive benefits, including better health, more social capital, and less social fragmentation, are brought about by increasing walkability through higher-quality public areas. Through enhanced transportation and accessibility, the design of public places significantly influences how easily people with decreased mobility can integrate into society (Dannenberg, et al. 2003). According to a study that examined children's behavior and social capital in the United States, kids in low-social-capital neighborhoods were 33 percent less likely to be active (meaning three or more days of physical activity the previous week) and 66 percent more likely to be inactive (meaning zero days of physical activity the previous week) (Kaczynski and Glover 2012). Less urban fragmentation and aesthetic degradation can be achieved through citizen-focused design. Low- and middle-income groups have a lower likelihood of owning a vehicle from a socioeconomic perspective. As a result, expanding public transportation reduces socioeconomic disparity (Speck 2012). According to another study (Leyden, K.M. 2003), Residents of highly "walkable," mixed-use neighborhoods "exhibited at least 80% stronger levels of four markers of social capital (knowing neighbors, sociability, trust, and political participation) than those in car-dependent neighborhoods,"

2.1.3 Environmental benefits

There are numerous environmental advantages to encouraging the growth of pedestrian-friendly public spaces in cities. By choosing to walk or bike instead of driving a car, one can cut down greenhouse gas emissions like carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other air pollutants in densely populated areas. In the long term, this can lessen the severity of climate change. Less atmospheric CO₂ results in better overall air quality and a more pleasant landscape, along with having an impact on respiratory diseases (air pollution alone causes over three million deaths per year). According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), resource-efficient communities with co-located housing, jobs, mixed land use, and easy access to public transit can reduce urban emissions by about 25%.

2.1.4 Public health-related benefits

Promoting walkability is an efficient approach to increasing life expectancy, lowering the incidence of diseases linked to sedentary lifestyles, and enhancing the quality of life. Moreover, Physical and mental health is enhanced by active transportation methods like cycling and walking (Cook et al.,2022). Exercise has been shown to significantly improve people's health and prevent chronic illnesses like diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular disease, and respiratory disease. Sedentary behavior has been identified by the WHO as the fourth most important risk factor for mortality, accounting for almost 3,2 million deaths worldwide (World Health Organization, 2015). Urban areas that are accessible, well-connected, and barrier-free increase the mobility freedom of older people, children, persons with disabilities, and their carers, enhancing their well-being and sense of inclusion. In addition, welcoming walking and cycling environments increase road safety, and lower injury, fall, and traffic accident rates. Environmental variables like air pollution, noise pollution, and harsh weather also have an impact on health. The biggest environmental health risk in Europe is air pollution, which accounts for the majority of fuel oil and vehicle emissions and results in over 400.000 premature deaths annually. In contrast, noise pollution from traffic accounts for about 8.900 of these deaths (European Environmental Agency, 2018).

2.1.5 Economic benefits

Cities with more walkable neighborhoods draw greater investment and can also aid families in cutting costs associated with motorized car use. Additionally, lowering morbidity and mortality has a favorable economic impact because illnesses can have negative economic consequences. The revitalization of commercial districts is another economic gain of increasing walkability (streets with a large number of businesses). Evidence shows that shops inside pedestrian areas or with traffic-mitigating schemes are more successful than those outside of them. Additionally, the usage of vehicles results in a variety of public costs for infrastructure including roads and parking lots, traffic jams, crash risks, and environmental harm (Murphy and Delucchi 1998; Litman 2010). These external expenditures are decreased when travel is switched from motorized to non-powered modes. The graph (Figure 3) contrasts the expected external costs of driving a

car versus walking. Moving from driving to walking can save you on average 25¢ per vehicle mile, and 50¢ per vehicle mile during urban peak hours.

Figure 3: Estimated External Costs of Automobile Travel and Walking (Litman 2009)

To better understand the impact of the 15-minute city concept, a comprehensive table that summarizes the potential impact of 15-minute city policy is given below (Table 1). The table provides insights into how the 15-minute city policy can affect the economy, social cohesion, health, and the environment. By examining these different dimensions, we can gain a more holistic understanding of the benefits that the 15 minute city concept can bring to urban communities. From the table, we can see that there is enormous potential for the 15-minute city policy to generate positive impacts across multiple areas. For example, by creating safe, walkable streets that prioritize pedestrians and cyclists over cars, we can not only reduce air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions but also promote physical activity and improve public health. Similarly, by designing streets that are conducive to social interaction and community engagement, we can foster a sense of belonging and increase social cohesion, which in turn can lead to greater economic prosperity and overall well-being.

Impact area	Benefit
Economy	Reinforce and support local business
	Urban regeneration
	City attractiveness
	Cost saving in public and private motorized transport
	Promotes tourism
	Creation of new job opportunities
	Enhance creative thinking and productivity
	Reduces motor vehicle maintenance in household expenses
	Reduce public health cost from chronic and environmental related diseases
	Reduces road infrastructure maintenance costs
Social	Improve social cohesion and equality
	Healing spatial segregation
	Placemaking and identity: sense of place and communities
	Improve safety
	Improve wellbeing
	Promote citizen engagement

Health	Promote more active lifestyle
	Healthier environment
	Reduce falls and road accidents
	Improve air quality
	Accessible healthy food
	Less risk of chronic diseases
	Reduce of environmental health risk by noise and air pollution.
Environmental	Reduce carbon emissions and energy consumption
	Reduce noise pollution
	Improve air quality
	Improve urban microclimate
	Increase greenery
	Reduce carbon footprint by consuming local products

Table 1: Impacts of the street redesign in line with the 15-minute city concept (EIT Urban Mobility Next 9, 2022)

2.2 Walkability as a sustainable urban public policy and its relation to housing affordability:

Many cities have embraced the concept of walkability as a means of achieving sustainable cities and have put in place a variety of infrastructures to support it. A number of positive

benefits, including greater health, more social capital, and less social fragmentation, are brought about by increasing walkability through higher-quality public areas (Saez, 2015). Residents of more-walkable neighborhoods, generally defined as those with mixed land uses (particularly residential and commercial), moderate to high densities, well-connected street networks, access to transit, and pedestrian infrastructures, such as sidewalks and street trees, have been shown to have lower rates of obesity and other medical conditions (Frank & Engelke, 2005), as well as more social connections and enhanced social capital (Leyden, 2003). A decrease in automotive dependence is expected to have environmental benefits as well, with fewer vehicle miles traveled (VMT) resulting in reduced carbon emissions and air pollution (Frank, et al., 2006).

There is growing concern that lower-income and disadvantaged groups are routinely being excluded from walkable areas given the many advantages of walkability and the rising demand for urban spaces and lifestyles in American cities (Brueckner, 2009; Myers, 2016). Potential gentrification-related displacement of these populations may be contributing to a significant spatial inequality where people who would benefit most from walkable and transit-oriented areas may find it increasingly difficult to afford them (Riggs, 2014).

Since academics and practitioners are becoming increasingly concerned that the growing popularity and demand for walkable urban areas would drive poor people out of city centers by driving up housing costs in amenity-rich neighborhoods. And because there is uncertainty about whether walkable urban neighborhoods have less affordable housing or if this would result in gentrification, numerous case studies that focus on the same problem were examined in order to evaluate the relationship between neighborhood walkability and housing affordability.

A comparative study was conducted (Bereitschaft, 2019) in three American cities—Charlotte, NC, Pittsburgh, PA, and Portland, In order to determine whether walkable urban neighborhoods have high housing prices from the perspective of both neighborhood residents and households within the surrounding metropolitan area that wants to move to that particular neighborhood. At the metropolitan level, those 3 cities have a combined population of almost 2 million people. In that study, affordability for both homeowners and renters is taken into account using the complete housing

affordability index (CHAI). Affordability for owners was calculated using the ratio of median income to qualifying income (the income required to buy a home of median value within a geographic area): according to the housing affordability index (HAI) published by the National Association of Realtors. The results of that study show that while housing was significantly less affordable for those households already living in neighborhoods with higher walkability indices, they were not significantly less affordable for those living in other parts of the metro. This seems to apply to renters more than to homeowners. This implies that housing is less affordable for families already living in walkable neighborhoods mainly due to lower household income rather than the increased housing costs. That is, median-earning households do not typically "view" more walkable neighborhoods as having higher housing costs. Housing stress may only be severe for renters and households earning less than the median income who already reside in walkable neighborhoods.

Among the three case-study US cities, walk score was a significant predictor of house affordability in only two models (renters only): Pittsburgh on a neighborhood level and Portland on a metropolitan level. interestingly in Pittsburgh, walk score was not a significant predictor of housing affordability for either homeowners or renters separately, but it was significant when taking into account both homeowners and renters at once using the combined housing affordability index. At the neighborhood level in Pittsburgh and the metropolitan level in Portland, housing affordability was inversely correlated with a walk score. Therefore, the study's findings conclude that, with the exception of Portland, no statistically significant relationship between housing affordability and walkability was observed at the metropolitan scale. So median income households in many parts of the city currently have adequate access to affordable housing in walkable neighborhoods located within their metropolitan areas.

Another study (De Nadai, 2018) was conducted to examine how neighborhood attributes like safety and walkability influence the cost of housing. For this experiment, 70000 houses across 7 Italian cities were considered. The study employed OpenStreetMap and Urban Atlas to gather geographic information on the nearby neighborhoods' amenities. And Census data as well as additional sources were used to calculate the population and building statistics. The study's findings revealed that individuals care about accessibility to amenities (such as parks and train stations), as well as intangible variables like the

feeling of security, which they think is one of the most crucial ones. In addition, the study indicated that neighborhood attributes like walkability and safety account for more than 20% of a house's value.

There is typically a positive correlation between walkability and home prices can be found when looking at case studies like these carried out in different locations. Some studies claim that the quality of neighborhood services is important as well. For instance, some disadvantaged neighborhoods have amenities nearby, but such amenities are subpar compared to those found in major cities. (Gunn et al.,2022) claim in their study, although walkability was found to be significantly associated with house prices, its magnitude was moderate and variable depending on how disadvantaged a neighborhood was. For instance, during their study, they discovered a negative correlation between house prices in more disadvantaged neighborhoods and positive associations in less disadvantaged neighborhoods. Since the positive correlation between walkability and housing prices can be identified in the majority of cities, policymakers should take measures to regulate housing costs or provide access to cheap housing to prevent gentrification.

2.3 Social Cohesion and Social Capital in 15-minute cities:

The 15-minute city policy's measures, such as creating more public spaces, giving priority to pedestrians, and adding more pedestrian-friendly routes, promote social interaction and social well-being. The results of Barcelona's superblocks also demonstrate that after the superblocks were implemented, residents reported greater well-being and tranquility in the neighborhoods which also offered them comfort and better mental health (Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona, 2021). Communities that are walkable provide opportunities for social engagement and personal interaction. In these communities, people can walk with family members or friends, stop to chat with neighbors while walking their dog, or walk with a friend to a local store or bus stop, these interactions facilitate and strengthen the personal bonds that bring people and communities together, creating more social cohesion and social capital (McLaren,2016). Also, the presence of public spaces that facilitate community networks and social support has a potential

benefit on health and social well-being through the feeling of community, the feeling of security, and social networks in the neighborhood [Mehdipanah et al, 2019].

Moreover, A key finding from a survey of two New Hampshire Communities found that higher levels of social capital are found in areas that are perceived to be more walkable (Rogers et al.,2014). In that study, many of the survey questions, including those that asked participants about their levels of trust for their neighbors and other community members as well as how frequently they participated in community events like public meetings or committees, were statistically analyzed and divided into two indices: community and trust. As we can see in the table below, the levels of community involvement and trust were higher among people who walked to more locations in their neighborhood or community. Therefore, the study demonstrates that more walkable communities are associated with higher social capital. Social capital is a key component of thriving, interconnected communities and the kinds of social networks that improve quality of life and well-being.

CHARACTERISTIC	MORE WALKABLE	LESS WALKABLE
DEMOGRAPHICS		
AVERAGE AGE	50	54
VERY OR MODERATELY CONSERVATIVE	22%	33%
VERY OR MODERATELY LIBERAL	47%	32%
VERY HAPPY	33%	25%
EXCELLENT HEALTH	27%	21%
AVERAGE INCOME RANGE	\$62,500-\$87,500	\$62,500-\$87,500
AVERAGE EDUCATION LEVEL	BACHELOR'S DEGREE	BACHELOR'S DEGREE
ATTEND RELIGIOUS SERVICES ALMOST EVERY WEEK OR MORE OFTEN	24%	27%
NEIGHBORHOOD PHYSICAL PERCEPTIONS		
AVERAGE NUMBER OF PLACES CAN WALK TO (OUT OF 13 OPTIONS)	10	3
HOW MANY MINUTES ARE YOU WILLING TO WALK TO A DESTINATION?	21	19
TRAVEL BEHAVIOR		
WALK EVERY DAY OR SEVERAL TIMES PER WEEK	55%	23%
BIKE EVERY DAY OR SEVERAL TIMES PER WEEK	11%	5%
RESIDENTS WHO COMMUTE TO WORK	71%	67%
OF THOSE WHO COMMUTE, % GOING BY CAR	89%	95%
SOCIAL CAPITAL METRICS		
PEOPLE CAN BE TRUSTED*	41%	27%
REPORTED TRUSTING NEIGHBORS A LOT*	52%	41%
PARTICIPATE IN A COMMUNITY PROJECT IN LAST LAST YEAR*	55%	43%
HAVE FRIENDS AT YOUR HOME IN LAST YEAR*	95%	91%
VOLUNTEERED IN LAST YEAR*	75%	67%
ATTENDED CLUB MEETING IN LAST YEAR*	67%	58%
AGREE THAT TV IS MY MAIN FORM OF ENTERTAINMENT	37%	47%

Table 2: Comparison of the responses (Rogers et al.,2014)

Since promoting walkability is one of the main goals of the 15-minute city policy, we may conclude that the 15-minute city urban policy can foster social capital in neighborhoods and foster social cohesiveness.

2.4 Beneficiaries of the 15-minute city policy:

- **City residents:** The inhabitants of the city are the direct beneficiary groups the policy intends to address. The goal of the policy is to directly benefit city residents in the following ways: better health and quality of life; shorter commutes; more free time; advantages of active travel for both physical and mental health; cleaner air; easy access to healthy food options; quality green space; and stronger community ties that lessen loneliness.
- **Disadvantaged and vulnerable communities-**

The policy also intends to address the requirements of disadvantaged communities and provide for those needs that have been previously unmet or difficult to satisfy. Numerous categories have been identified and are listed below to help better understand the groups that make up vulnerable populations.

1. **Elderly-** This policy aims to meet the requirements of senior citizens. The essential services will be available within a 15-minute walk for them. Moreover, according to several studies, loneliness is a common problem for the elderly. This strategy will encourage walking, help them connect with new people, and help them overcome loneliness.
2. **Households earning below medium income-** Low-income families frequently reside in the suburbs without access to private vehicles, forcing them to rely on public transportation. They will benefit from this strategy because they can find all the necessary services in their neighborhood and meet their needs within a 15-minute walk. Also, the policy promotes local employment opportunities therefore these people will have more employment options than before. Furthermore, the encouragement of walking and bicycling for all people in this policy also promotes equality, eradicating any sense of inferiority among those without access to a private vehicle.
3. **People with disabilities-** By enhancing accessibility and increasing the number of public spaces, this policy would improve the lives of those with disabilities who previously lacked access to essential services and public spaces. The policy is also

putting in place steps to facilitate home delivery options, which will greatly help disabled persons.

4. **People prone to diseases-** The 15-minute city policy would significantly cut down the amount of car usage and CO2 emissions. As a result, the citizens of the city would benefit from improved health. Studies have shown how city air pollution impacts those with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Therefore, the people who are prone to such diseases can directly benefit from this policy.
 - **Employees:** Employees can significantly reduce the amount of time and money they spend traveling to work each day. In 2019, One in four Europeans spend between 30 and 59 minutes getting to and from work. Additionally, in 2018, 13.2% of families' consumer spending in the EU was on transportation. Also, this policy encourages the culture of working from home. Therefore, the 15-minute city policy will benefit the employees by cutting off their commuting time and reducing expenditure on transportation.
 - **Children-** The 15-minute city policy intends to increase the number of public places that include children's play areas. Studies have shown in various cities that the adoption of comparable policies that promote walkability and the extension of public spaces has resulted in more interaction amongst kids in play areas.
 - **Startups, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises-** The purpose of the 15-minute city is to make it easier for local residents to find the necessities of life without having to travel far. This policy will create a favorable setting for the development of neighborhood and home-based businesses that provide a range of options to improve local employment, minority entrepreneurship, wage growth, and family self-sufficiency. Given that COVID-19 had a higher impact on small businesses, this will be a good opportunity for small businesses to prosper. moreover, in many cities, the government invites small and medium-sized businesses to suggest projects that would help realize the 15-minute city policy. Some companies even work with governments to give technological and other support for the achievement of the goal.
 - **Sustainable transportation companies-** since 15-minute city promotes the use of bicycles, the companies that manufacture bicycles, and e-bikes will indirectly benefit from this policy.

2.5 Current exclusion in urban accessibility for the elderly and disabled and immigrants:

There are many discussions in the literature about how vulnerable people such as the elderly, disabled, refugees, and immigrants are excluded from numerous services in an urban context. It is crucial to analyze the difficulties that vulnerable people are now dealing with in urban settings in order to design and incorporate methods into policy that will address these concerns and overcome obstacles to achieve social inclusion.

2.5.1 Green space accessibility

In order to understand the challenges refugees encounter in accessing the city's natural spaces, a study was done by interviewing their experiences in Berlin, London, and Sheffield. The study concentrated on green space typologies such as the network of publicly accessible squares, parks, riversides, community growing plots, and sports fields. During the interview, participants mentioned feeling uneasy about going into urban parks and other public places in general. These encounters had two main components: uncertainty about how to interpret various social norms in various settings, and concerns about personal safety. Some users mentioned they found them to be unwelcoming, unpleasant, and alienating. Moreover, nearly all of the interviewees described first- or second-hand experiences with abuse and hate crimes in public settings and were highly aware of their own vulnerability in this regard. The impressions of public spaces, including parks, were inevitably shaped by these explicit abusive behaviors. 'Parks are frequently considered as a place for indigenous people and not for individuals who arrived from overseas' says Zenith (Rishbeth, C et al., 2019). As part of the 15-minute city policy, many urban green spaces have been built. There is evidence, nevertheless, that refugees encounter difficulties accessing these benefits currently. Therefore, the policy must also take into account potential remedies based on the local situation.

According to the literature, people with a disability have a strong desire to visit natural areas and participate in social activities (Chikuta et al., 2019). Therefore, it is crucial to identify and address any obstacles preventing people with disabilities from accessing urban parks to ensure that everyone has equal access. Another study evaluated the

accessibility and quality of urban parks in Warsaw as described by those who have mobility issues (seniors, blind, and partially sighted people) through in-depth interviews (IDI) and "walk-and-talk" interviews. Four essential characteristics of a place—accessibility and connections, comfort and image, uses and activities, and sociability—were taken into account. The study results indicate a problem of accessibility of urban parks for people with mobility difficulties. To put it in detail, it was discovered during the survey that the majority of participants had some issues and paid close attention to the unfriendly infrastructure surrounding the parks. For example, blind people reported having the most trouble getting to the park. It was challenging because there were no tactile surfaces directing people to any gates in the park, no signs indicating that the gates were closed, and simply a considerably narrower wicket gate providing access to the entry. Moreover, it is also reported that there aren't enough park entrances or that they aren't big enough, or that the transit links aren't good enough. To sum it up, In the 21st century, people with a disability still face problems when trying to access public spaces (Wojnowska-Heciak, M et al., 2022). The quality of the park is influenced by more than just the physical features; social factors are also significant. Encouragement of those with mobility difficulties to visit parks and the planning of more social events should improve social interaction. Anyone with mobility issues should not be prevented from going outside to breathe in the fresh air, and boost self-esteem.

2.5.2 Segregation

It is a well-established fact that immigrants are not equally distributed within OECD countries and tend to be concentrated in certain areas, especially within large cities (OECD, 2016). The neighborhood where immigrants live affects their chances of making contacts, learning the language, and getting access to things like housing, schools, potential employers, and other resources. While the neighborhood can offer new chances it can also limit integration outcomes. This concerns the situation of their future integration prospects and those of their descendants (International Migration Outlook, 2021). Residential segregation's effects on social integration and social cohesion, in general, have come under investigation because they are frequently linked to fewer interactions with host-country culture and customs. In fact, it is often believed that having a high concentration of immigrants will hinder integration (International Migration

Outlook, 2021). According to a 2017 survey, more than half of EU citizens believe that the lack of interactions between immigrants and the native-born is a "significant obstacle" to integration. This could have detrimental externalities on the host society as a whole (European Commission, 2018). These risks may be exacerbated when immigrants are concentrated in locations with inadequate infrastructure, limited access to public services and markets, subpar housing, and generally poorer amenities—which is quite prevalent throughout OECD countries (International Migration Outlook, 2021). This viewpoint on the residential segregation of immigrants primarily assumes that immigrants' first location choices are limited. This may occur due to financial constraints that prevent immigrants from living somewhere else, or discrimination in the housing market. Additionally, there are connections between the residential segregation of immigrants and more general patterns of socioeconomic residential segregation. Population with socioeconomic disadvantage will typically live in neighborhoods with more affordable housing or a higher share of social housing (International Migration Outlook, 2021).

A study examined the concept of the "neighborhood unit", its origins, and its influence to demonstrate the shaping mechanisms of racial segregation. The study made it evident that Perry and the prominent group of planners who adopted the concept believed it would improve the livability, vibrancy, and social cohesion of urban regions. However, their notion of a 'neighborhood unit' concept also promoted racial segregation in both residential areas and schools (Erickson, Highsmith, 2018)

Since the "neighborhood unit" concept and the "15-minute city" have many similarities and from the spatial planning perspective there are no differences between both concepts, it is unclear whether this idea will encourage segregation in metropolitan areas. Moreover, several criticisms like "by creating the city of the quarter, the city is building new walls and sinking into selfishness," writes Delaleu in the online magazine *Chroniques d'architecture*. He also claims that Hidalgo's vision excludes those who work as night watchmen, housekeepers, or construction workers who work in the prosperous center city but live in the poorer suburbs. However, no research has been done in cities where the 15-minute city policy is already in place to determine whether the 15-minute city policy truly increases or decreases segregation. There is therefore no proof that the 15-minute city will either discourage or promote segregation.

2.5.3 Social Capital and Refugee/Immigrant integration:

According to Robert Putnam (Putnam, 2020), social capital refers to the relationship between members of a community. The OECD describes social capital as “networks together with shared norms, values, and understandings that facilitate cooperation within or among groups” and as a real-world network between individuals (OECD, 2007). Social capital in a neighborhood positively affects the relationships between neighbors, coworkers, and friends in daily life. Neighborhoods with high social capital benefit society by fostering micro-level outcomes, such as better family well-being and community strength, and macro-level benefits, such as successful economies and vibrant society. (Stone, W. and Hughes, J. 2002). In addition to the aforementioned advantages of social capital in a neighborhood context, social capital can also aid in the integration of refugees and immigrants.

Another study (Ziller et al., 2022) examines how perceived social cohesion in a neighborhood influences the immigrant’s identity and their sense of belonging to the host community. The study conducted an interview that was carried out face-to-face in the first wave, and in the second wave, interviews took place either in a face-to-face setting or via a web survey. In total, 5312 responders were counted, distributed among 260 neighborhoods. Social cohesion is measured using the degree to which the following behaviors occur in respondents' neighborhoods—(i) people greet each other, (ii) people can be trusted, (iii) people get along well, (iv) people know each other, (v) people like to help each other, and (vi) people would speak up if youth were to cause trouble. All statements were evaluated on a scale with four response categories, higher numbers denote higher levels of perceived neighborhood social cohesion.

The findings of the study demonstrate a positive and statistically significant relationship between perceived neighborhood cohesion and immigrants' national identification. Therefore, the 15-minute city urban policy will aid in the integration of immigrants into local communities. However, no studies have been conducted in the neighborhoods where the 15-minute city policy is being implemented to determine how well immigrants have assimilated into the local communities. Furthermore, the goal of the 15-minute city, as stated in the literature, is to improve neighborhood variety by fostering communities

that reflect a wide range of cultures, ethnicities, and socioeconomic and social classes. However, it is unclear how or how these goals will be achieved.

2.6 Existing methods to evaluate the accessibility:

There are existing methodologies in the literature to evaluate the pedestrian accessibility of all the resident social groups to neighborhood services. For example, a study proposed an analytical model designed and developed utilizing a GIS-based model integrated with a Territorial Information System (TIS), which addresses the 15-minute city theme and evaluates the accessibility of neighborhood services for all resident social groups. The GIS-based model has been implemented by improving and integrating a Territorial Information System (TIS) previously adopted to assess pedestrian accessibility to neighborhood services (Caselli, B et al., 2018; Rossetti et al., 2020). The original TIS, which is managed with the ArcGIS software, is based on a vector data structure and includes a number of layers, including pedestrian paths, public amenities (such as schools and green spaces), traffic areas, buildings, and house numbers, all of which were implemented using open data and on-site inspections (Casellia et al., 2022). By using the population data obtained from the municipality a detailed spatial distribution map of the population can be defined to describe exactly how inhabitants are distributed within the neighborhood through a georeferencing process. And then, isochrone maps can be created by processing data to identify the catchment regions of selected collective facilities using the Service Area analysis tool in ArcGIS Network Analyst (Casellia et al., 2022). From the final output, we may determine the proportion of neighborhood residents who can access the nearby services in less than 10 or 15 minutes. Although, this methodology will be useful to assess pedestrian accessibility at the neighborhood level, this model didn't specifically take into account the speed of the vulnerable groups such as elderly and disabled, instead taking into account inhabitants' general access to surrounding amenities. This highlights the importance of using more nuanced and inclusive methods of accessibility assessment that take into account the needs of all population groups. This can help to ensure that services are accessible to everyone, regardless of age or ability, and can contribute to more equitable and sustainable communities.

Another study proposes a methodological framework based on network science techniques for evaluating 15-minute cities. network science methodologies have been widely used for examining human movement patterns, defining urban structures, and analyzing spatial interaction patterns (Batty, 2012).

The case study was carried out in the central city of Nanjing, the capital city of Jiangsu province, China. Data required for this method is Mobile phone signaling data which is used to estimate the working and employment population as well as obtain the actual mobility network (i.e., the origin-destination (OD) network between home and non-work activity locations) (Zhang et al., 2022) The data were provided by China Unicom, one of the largest telecommunication operators in China. A location is considered to be an activity point if a person spends more than 30 minutes there. Each person's residence and place of employment are identified in accordance with the following rules: If a person spends more time in an activity point between the hours of 9 pm and 8 am in a given month, the area will be regarded as their residence. Subsequently, the location will be considered as their place of employment if they spend the majority of their time in the activity point between the hours of 9 am and 5 pm within the same month. The population of each grid cell that lives there and works there is then determined using the locations of those places.

The availability of nearby urban facilities is assessed using point of interest (POI) data. The data are collected using the API of Gaode Maps one of the largest Chinese web map service providers. the network-based evaluation framework consists of three parts. First, a maximum flow algorithm is used to estimate the optimal mobility network based on the spatial distribution of urban facilities and population. Second, data from mobile phone signaling is used to determine the actual OD network. Third, the differences between the actual and optimal OD networks are measured in order to get insight into the extent to which human mobility patterns, as a reflection on the usage patterns of urban amenities, match or do not match the schemes of urban planning and construction.

Figure 4. Proposed network-based framework for evaluating 15-minute city (Zhang et al., 2022)

This method is used to identify the Locations where the provision of urban amenities does not match local needs based on the comparison between optimal mobility patterns and their actual counterparts. then, it looks at the built environment, demographic, and network structure elements that affect the observed mismatch problems.

These results suggest that the mismatch between supply and demand is more likely to happen in population-dense areas, as these areas are mostly associated with high density and diversity of built environment factors (Zhang et al., 2022). Despite the abundant urban amenities in the district, some of the amenities, such as businesses for luxury shopping or high-end catering, may not accommodate local residents' daily needs. Residents may instead go to amenities that are not nearby for proper service. As a result, a mismatch between supply and demand is observed.

Currently, the planning of a 15-minute city primarily builds upon a static view of allocating urban amenities based on population size (Da Silva et al., 2020). The case study, however, suggests that this static view could be problematic as the actual situation could be considerably different from the planning scheme. Identifying spatial mismatch issues that hinder the achievement of a 15-minute city and their ascribe factors will be critical for developing proper intervention strategies (Zhang et al., 2022).

2.7 list of the cities implementing the 15-minute city and similar policy:

The Mayor's Agenda for a Green and Just Recovery mentioned various cities and highlighted the projects they initiated as the first steps toward putting the 15-minute city plan into action. In addition, it was reported in a number of articles and newspapers that some cities have already begun to implement the 15-minute city policy while other cities have plans to do so. The cities on the list were listed below, along with the initiatives they initiated.

- **Milan** - Milan has committed to using the "15-minute city" as a framework for recovery in response to COVID-19. To avoid a spike in car usage, the city wants to ensure that all people can access important services on foot. They built 35 kilometers of new cycle lanes around the city as part of the initiative, and there have been numerous discussions to jointly devise strategies to promote teleworking. Moreover, the city also is upgrading streetscapes through its open squares and road programs, sustainable urban mobility strategy, and introduction of a 30 km/h city speed limit (down from 50 km/h) on 60% of the road network. Additionally, several initiatives have been put into practice in a number of neighborhoods as part of the 15-minute city strategy.
- **Paris**- Paris has adopted the notion of the "15-minute city" as well. To enable people to work safely closer to or at home, the city intends to build more coworking spaces, as well as promote remote work. moreover, it Expands the uses of existing amenities. for example, using libraries outside standard hours. using nightclubs as gyms during the day or having schools act as parks and play spaces over the weekend. The project also includes "greening," which includes adding more green space to already-existing public areas, establishing new parks and urban forests, and constructing new gardens for urban agriculture. Additionally, limiting car traffic near schools will make it safer for individuals to ride and walk. The city will also encourage local businesses, spaces, and places for sharing and trading to encourage the uptake of existing local enterprises.
- **Portland, USA**- Portland has converted more than 90 miles of congested roads into neighborhood greenways as part of the initiative, where street trees shade sidewalks, and green swales offer sustainable drainage and traffic calming. Additionally, it aims to develop complete neighborhoods, which feature a variety

of housing alternatives, grocery stores, and other commercial services that cater to the neighborhood.

- **Bogotá, Colombia-** To encourage the usage of bicycles, 35 km of bike lanes were built. A series of roadways, the 22-mile Ciclova network, that are typically restricted to cars on Sundays will now extend its restriction to other days of the week as well. Additionally, private bike rental companies are lending e-bikes to medical professionals. Moreover, As part of the "vital neighborhoods" vision, which aims to improve the quality of life by enhancing streets and neighborhoods, there are a number of priority zones for kids that are centered around daycare facilities.
- **London-** The city announced its new Street space Plan to encourage walking and bicycling while easing pressure on public transportation and fostering social distancing. The plan intends to build a planned bicycle network with new routes to change neighborhood town centers, enable safe walking and cycling journeys, support a local economic recovery, and lessen residential street traffic through low-traffic neighborhoods throughout London.
- **Montréal, Canada-** In response to COVID-19, they intend to construct 327km of bike lanes. In accordance with public health regulations, the routes will offer specialized, secure facilities that will enable people to reach the city's significant parks and a number of main commercial arteries, among other things. The city is also spending money to expand delivery services using bicycles and electric vehicles. The city is also investing in increasing bicycle and electric vehicle delivery services.
- **Seattle, United States of America-** Twenty miles, more than 2.5 million square feet of Seattle's streets will be permanently closed to traffic so that locals can use them for walking, bicycling, and other forms of exercise. One street-selection criterion was that routes connect people to essential services. In order to support the general goal of preventing a return to high levels of traffic and accompanying pollution as the city proceeds toward recovery, the city will also expedite the building of bike infrastructure.
- **Melbourne, Australia-** The city devised a Movement and Place framework, guided by Local Livability research, and started executing a 20-minute pilot program in three locations. This framework puts people at the center of

transportation planning. According to a city study, people will walk for no more than 20 minutes to fulfill their daily necessities locally.

- **Rome-** C40's Reinventing Cities program aims to promote sustainable growth and highlight creative responses to urban and environmental problems. Under this initiative, a project called "Campo Urbano" was proposed and planned by FRESIA For the development of the Rome Tuscolana site: an urban car-free zone integrated into a consolidated residential and industrial sector. Leveraging education, career advancement, and culture to promote urban renewal. A true mixed-use development that supports the 15-minute city and integrated mobility with homes, workplaces, flexible spaces, a student hotel, an energy center, and retail. one of the project's essential components are converting a 5ha disused railroad yard into a car-free, mixed-use area in line with the "15-minute city" model.
- **Edinburgh, UK-** According to council leader Adam McVey, the idea of 20-minute neighborhoods is close to becoming a reality in Edinburgh. Making as much as feasible accessible locally aligns with efforts to reduce the use of cars, strengthen underprivileged neighborhoods, and assist local businesses in the wake of the pandemic. Councillor McVey remarked, "This is a policy where the climate agenda and the poverty reduction agenda come together." A significant mixed-use regeneration project is currently being pursued by the municipality, and the proposed master plan has been expanded to incorporate nearby abandoned bowling greens. Instead of a "typical infill housing scheme," the project will produce 260 dwellings, at least 35% of which will be affordable, along with a new nursery with 128 spaces, seven new commercial buildings, and additional public open space. Additionally, the nearby B-listed historic old stable block will be renovated into a venue for community gatherings and creative workspaces.
- **Dublin, Ireland-** as of now Dublin is not a 15-minute city. But the Dublin city development plan 2022-2028. However, the 15-minute city concept is included in Section 5.5.3 of the Dublin City Development Plan 2022–2028."Healthy Placemaking and the 15 Minute City," Promoting the 15 Minute City concept is the main goal. Sustainable neighborhoods, which serve as community hubs and offer a variety of uses, housing tenures, and housing typologies, Policy QHSN10. This policy seeks to strengthen the bond between residents and the communities in which they reside By preserving local character and promoting an asset-based approach to the location, design, and management of new development, The goal

is to create 'liveable' communities and urban environments that are appealing, distinctive, inclusive, safe, secure, age-friendly, accessible, walkable, and healthy.

- **Brussels, Belgium** - The Flemish Association for Space and Planning (VRP) said that experts advise a Flemish master plan to introduce the notion of the fifteen-minute city everywhere (Spinks, 2020). More than 200 Flemish municipal advisers, urbanists, and mobility experts met during the coronavirus crisis to discuss ways to make towns and villages healthier. In order to give back the Belgian capital to its citizens, the city intends to create "10-minute cities" that will allow residents to walk to any facility, park, school, or retail establishment in under ten minutes. Encouraging more walking will make Brussels a safer and healthier place for residents to live. However, since it's not always possible to remain in your neighborhood, the city has planned to implement policies that promote mobility while lowering traffic and pollution. Therefore, Brussels' active mobility policy has been strengthened through the creation of various options to be active while traveling, such as city bike rentals, and innovative parking solutions, as well as the construction of more than 35 kilometers of cycle routes since 2014. For example, the FEDER 2014–20 project Cycloparking installed secure bike parking boxes throughout the city to relieve residents of the strain of finding a secure place to store their bicycles (Spinks, 2020).
- **Barcelona, Spain** - The first "superblock" strategy was used in Barcelona's Poblenou neighborhood. With the purpose of reclaiming for citizens some of the space currently used by private automobiles, the Superblock strategy is moving one step further and becoming the model for street transformation for the entire city. The objective is to establish a public place that fosters social interactions and the local economy while also being healthier, greener, fairer, and safer. This strategy has resulted in an increase in ground-level commercial firms by 31%, from 65 to 85, demonstrating a positive impact on commercial activity.
- **Nantes, France**- On the Île of Nantes, the Prairie-au-Duc neighborhood is frequently used as an example of the concept of the 15-minute city. The district, which is the result of a more than 15-year redevelopment initiative, brings together stores, services, and common public amenities. The quarter-hour city concept was made possible on the scale of this district because of the freedom of programming.

- **Detroit, USA-** The city of Detroit is now planning to create 20-minute neighborhoods. A city-wide objective set by Mayor Duggan is to create and construct walkable neighborhoods where residents can access high-quality shops, make use of amenities in open spaces, and travel to transit and/or multi-modal options within a 20-minute walk. The effort aims to provide households with a 20-minute walk radius across the attractive, safe, and productive territory. The 20-Minute Neighborhood objectives must be met by Detroit within this framework, as these initiatives will lay the groundwork for the lower east side of Detroit's future success. The city has also increased its network of bicycle lanes from 13 miles to 240 as part of achieving the 20-minute neighborhood. Moreover, a mixed-use project being built by Gensler in Detroit called 'Infill on the Cut', will include 350 residential units, 80,000 square feet of retail space, and 18,000 square feet of green space. Once put into practice, the master plan of this project will bridge the gap between downtown Detroit and the neighborhoods surrounding Eastern Market by creating exciting, areas where people can live, shop, and play.
- **New York, USA-** New York has begun to embrace the 15-minute city through a variety of processes. For instance, through comprehensive engagement, the city's 'myPB' participatory budgeting process has allotted \$120 million to 706 community-designed projects over the previous eight years, improving local services (C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, & C40 Knowledge Hub, 2020) Additionally, as an effort to promote flexible use of buildings and public space, New York City permits food stands and farmer's markets to use its parking lots and schoolyards on weekends. Furthermore, Former United States Secretary of Housing and Urban Development Shaun Donovan has adopted the concept as a key to his New York City mayoral candidacy.
- **Ottawa, Canada-** One of the first Canadian cities to explicitly include the 15 Minute City in their planning documents is the City of Ottawa. Ottawa's new Official Plan for 2021 contains five broad policy reforms referred to as the "Five Big Moves." The 15 Minute City is mentioned under the policies "growth management," "urban and community design," and "environment, energy, and public health." The City's goal is to develop existing neighborhoods while also fostering their development into walkable 15-minute neighborhoods with a diversified mix of land uses, such as a variety of homes, stores, services, nearby access to food, schools, employment, parks, greenspaces, and walkways.

- **Singapore-** In Singapore, the Land Transport Authority outlines a long-term objective for an integrated approach to transport planning in its Land Transport Master Plan 2040 (LTMP 2040). In accordance with the LTMP 2040, residents should be able to travel around the town in 20 minutes and throughout the entire city in 45 minutes or less. Numerous initiatives were mentioned, including priority for buses, connecting more destinations by train, additional bicycle lanes, and more integrated transport hubs. Additionally, they plan to implement various initiatives like priority queues, the new technology MAVIS to make it easier for those who are blind to access transportation, additional wheelchair-accessible facilities, and additional resting areas to ensure that all demographic groups of the population receive equal benefits.
- **Hamilton, New Zealand-** the city is planning to implement a 20-minute neighborhood. According to Eeva-Liisa Wright, General Manager of Infrastructure Operations, the Council and Waka Kotahi NZ Transport Agency had already taken actions that were consistent with a 20-Minute City (A 20-minute life-changer, 2020). Additionally, she claims that there are currently planned or anticipated transportation and infrastructure programs. In order to comprehend and predict movements throughout the city and to enhance connectivity, data-driven research on bicycle and pedestrian movements is being created. A transport-led growth strategy for the region as a whole is being developed, and mass transit planning as part of the Hamilton-Auckland Corridor Plan has been ongoing for some years. The government is now considering a number of projects, and decisions regarding which ones will be funded nationwide as part of the 20-minute program are anticipated within the next several months.
- **China-** China's masterplans for **Shanghai, Guangzhou**, and other cities all incorporate 15-Minute Community Life Circles. Another city using a polycentric strategy for urban development is **Chengdu**, which has a 'Great City' plan to build a smaller, unique satellite city outside of the city where everything will be accessible by mass transit and within a 15-minute walk of the pedestrianized center. Furthermore, Shanghai started working on the concept of a "15-minute community life circle" in 2014 and included it in its master plan for 2035. Shanghai has developed a comprehensive response plan, according to Xu Yisong, director of the city's Urban Planning and Natural Resources Bureau, and more than 180 projects have been successfully completed to enhance the community's environment and services.

- **Buenos Aires-** the city is trying to improve walking and cycling infrastructure and deliver green space, fresh food markets, health facilities, recycling centers, and other amenities to every neighborhood, including by establishing one of the largest car-free zones in the world.
- **Utrecht, Netherlands-** Utrecht city has released its vision for the year 2040 to turn Utrecht into the '10-minute city'. The city is anticipated to have a population of roughly 455,000 in 20 years. In order to ensure that our city is a safe and enjoyable location for these individuals to live and work, the vision contains a number of plans for the city. To prevent the city from becoming too hot, too dry, or too wet as the climate changes, the city is planning to build more green spaces and waterways. They also intend to build more green spaces like parks throughout the city while making sure they are accessible. In addition, the city intends to build urban centers in other parts of the city. These facilities are known as 'hubs'. A hub is a location where many roads and public transportation routes converge, as well as a location where more residences, amenities, workplaces, and healthcare facilities can be constructed. The new hub locations include Lunetten-Koningsweg, Overvecht, Papendorp, Westraven, Central Leidsche Rijn, and the Utrecht Science Park (the area around the university). To efficiently manage the space, the city intends to implement a barcode model. This model helps to choose the best way to utilize the limited area available. for example, do we build at ground level? Do we build underground? Or do we build upwards? they are also making sure that buildings and public spaces are used for multiple purposes. Buildings that have shops at ground level, offices above, and homes higher up. Homes that are suitable for working from home. Therefore, promoting mixed-used neighborhoods.
- **Copenhagen, Denmark-** To promote liveability and sustainability, Nordhavn in Copenhagen has been constructed as a "five-minute city," making it easy to reach stores, institutions, workplaces, cultural facilities, and public transportation within five minutes of walking from any point in the district. This strategy combines precise planning for infrastructure, architecture, urban design, and landscaping with strategic development that emphasizes socioeconomics, stakeholder management, and policymaking. The district will grow over the next 50 years to accommodate 40,000 people and 40,000 workplaces (Deichmann, 2020). From any location in the district, people may walk for five minutes to find shops, institutions, workplaces, cultural facilities, and public transportation. A bicycle

network and elevated metro track will serve the region, forming a "green artery." The elevated track serves to cover the bicycle motorway so that cyclists may ride through all-weather situations while remaining dry.

Finally, a few publications have mentioned that the 15-minute policy has started to be applied in cities like **Turin**, **Delhi**, and **Bangalore**. However, there isn't much information available regarding the list of projects that are being implemented as part of the 15-minute policy.

The list of cities that are adopting the similar policy is summarized in the table (table 3) below, along with the policy's name and its objective.

City	Policy	Objective
Milan	15-minute city policy	Making neighborhoods self-sufficient, enhance public places and encourage public transportation.
Paris	ville du quart d'heure	Creation of co-working spaces, green spaces, enhance local business.
Portland, USA	20-Minute neighborhoods	Encourage sustainable transportation
Bogotá, Colombia	15-minute city	Accessible urban places
London	15-minute neighborhoods	Improve access to essential amenities
Montréal, Canada	15-minute city	Create livable and inclusive neighborhoods
Seattle, USA	Seattle 2035 plan	Create compact, walkable and livable neighborhoods.
Melbourne, Australia	15-minute city	Reduce reliance on cars and promote sustainable transportation.
Rome	15-minute city	Encourage sustainable transportation
Edinburgh, UK	15-minute city	Promote public transit, connected communities
Dublin, Ireland	15-minute city	create 'liveable' communities and urban environment
Brussels, Belgium	10-minute city	lowering traffic and pollution, healthier neighborhoods.
Barcelona, Spain	Superblock strategy	street transformation, establish a public place that fosters social interactions

Nantes, France	15-minute city	Creating more green spaces and public areas
Detroit, USA	20-minute neighborhoods	Enhance public place and promote public transportation.
New York, USA	15-minute city	community-designed projects, improving local services
Ottawa, Canada	15-minute neighborhoods	diversified mix of land uses, access to several essential services.
Singapore	20-minute neighborhoods	Enhance public transportation and public places
Hamilton, New Zealand	20-minute neighborhoods	Implement infrastructure programs, promote public transportation
China	15-minute city	Self-sufficient neighborhoods, sustainable urbanization
Buenos Aire	15-minute city	Improve walking and cycling infrastructure, enhance green space
Utrecht, Netherlands	10-minute city	more green spaces, urban centers, enhance public transportation
Copenhagen, Denmark	five-minute city	forming a green artery, prioritize cyclists and pedestrians.

Table 3 list of the cities implementing the 15-minute city and similar policy:

2.7.1 Similar strategies:

The 15-minute city is not the only urban model that focuses on walkability and proximity. In fact, there are several models that seem to focus on the same goal i.e., prioritizing walking and cycling to make cities and their citizens healthier.

- 20-minute neighborhoods- Melbourne
- 5-Minute Neighborhood- Copenhagen
- 10-minute neighborhood- Utrecht
- Superblocks - Barcelona
- A walkable city
- complete neighborhoods

- Compact city
- Car-free city- Hamburg

2.8 Impact evaluation of similar strategies

To gain insights into how the 15-minute city urban policy could improve the environment and people, impact evaluation studies for comparable initiatives were sought. The Superilla (Superblock) model from Barcelona was chosen because it embodies the "15-minute city" concept and the results of the policy have been made available to the public.

Superblocks- Barcelona

In May 2016, the government of the city of Barcelona approved the government measure "Omplim de vida els carrers" (Let's fill the streets with life), with the intention of bringing the city's operations closer to the new environmental challenges and opportunities for improving the quality of life of people. The goal is to make Barcelona a liveable city, with more activity on the streets. The strategy employed to accomplish this goal is the implementation of "Superilles" (superblocks) in Barcelona. Superblocks interventions have been carried out in three Barcelona neighborhoods since 2016: Poblenou, Sant Antoni, and Horta. The Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona has assessed the environmental and health effects as part of the Salut als Carrers (Health in the Streets) program and urban transformations and has published a results report (Palència et al., 2020). The evaluation was conducted using both quantitative and qualitative methods, including pre-and post-intervention health surveys, focus groups, environmental measurements of air quality, an observational study of physical activity, an audit to evaluate the change in the neighborhood's walkability, and two ethnographic guerrillas, which combine observation and semi-structured interviews.

Interventions in Poblenou:

- pacification of motorized traffic prioritizing passers-by and bicycles.
- creation of new spaces for staying in sections of the old streets and their confluences freed from traffic.
- Creation of picnic tables, literary tours, spaces for occasional markets and sports and children's play areas

Interventions in Sant Antoni

- pacification of two streets (Comte Borrell and Tamarit), totaling four sections of roadway, with the construction of an 1800 m² public square at the junction.
- More open space is reserved for passers-by, together with new living spaces for new purposes and more greenery, such as trees and plants.
- expansion of the superblock

Interventions in Horta:

- Pacification of the neighborhood's main entrance street (Fulton and Horta), with the addition of a single platform, and a 10 km/h speed limit.
- Construction of a single platform and the elimination of parking spaces in two streets (Feliu Codina and Chap), which had several public and private facilities and almost no sidewalks.
- Reduced parking and the construction of living spaces on Eduard Toda Street are part of a tactical intervention that is temporary, low-cost, and reversible.

The effect of superblocks on health and their determinants:

A conceptual framework was created to explain the potential effects of superblocks on population health as well as the underlying mechanisms and connections between them [Mehdipanah et al., 2019]. It describes the possible connections between superblocks and health, including how various interventions affect housing, transportation, and urban planning, ultimately affecting diverse health outcomes.

The interventions are expected to have effects both at the neighborhood level and at the individual level on its residents. On the one hand, a decrease in air and noise pollution and an improvement in traffic safety are anticipated at the neighborhood level, both of which have a direct impact on health and safety. There will also be additional outdoor places, which will encourage people to use the public space more frequently. Additionally, the spaces will be easier to navigate on foot, encouraging people to walk more and engage in greater physical activity. The presence of more people and fewer cars on the streets will improve the perception of safety. pedestrian-friendly areas encourage business and social interactions in public areas. However, such improvements obtained through various interventions can also make the neighborhood more attractive and produce adverse effects such as gentrification and displacement.

Figure 5. Conceptual framework of the effect of superblocks on health and its determinants (Salut als Carrers, 2021)

Results of Health studies

In order to make the analysis more understandable, The Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona divided its findings into three main categories:

- **Air pollution and noise**
- **Characteristics and usage of places**
- **Well-being and social contact.**

Due to the complexity of the intervention, different methodologies, both qualitative and quantitative, have been utilized to evaluate the environmental and health effects of the various superblocks.

Results in Horta:

Air and noise pollution- In Horta, noise and air pollution were measured using both air quality measurements and neighborhood perceptions.

Environmental Assessment on Air Quality- Measurements of the environment were made by ISGlobal using passive NO₂ collectors and black carbon sensors, as well as the mobile unit of the Barcelona Public Health Agency. The NO₂ and particle data collected by the mobile unit demonstrate that the pollutant concentrations recorded during the post-intervention period (2020–202) are lower than those recorded during the earlier period (2017). However, taking into account the reduced mobility and emissions brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic situations, which have resulted in an overall decline in air quality levels throughout the city. Therefore, the recorded pollutant concentrations are contextualized using a fixed reference station. When the measurements from the two evaluation stages are compared, the average NO₂ level after the intervention is found to have increased slightly (1.65 µg/m³ on average). Thus, the mobile unit's measurements of NO₂ and particle matter reveal that the urban intervention in the Horta superblock did not significantly affect air quality.

Individual Assessment-Air Quality and Noise- A survey of 1200 persons was conducted in the Horta superblock between May and September 2018 before the intervention, and 835 of those respondents responded again in September 2020 following the intervention. In the intervening area, roughly 45% of the women and 50% of the men who were interviewed said that noise levels had dropped, and about 50% believed that pollution levels had decreased. Although the percentages of pollution were identical, only 15% of men and 10% of women said that noise had decreased in the nearby streets, which would support the superblock's influence on lowering pollution in the intervened region. It must be noted, however, that roughly 23% of the population believed that street noise had grown and about 28% believed that pollution had increased.

Results in Sant Antoni

Environmental Assessment-Air Quality- The levels of the air pollutants NO₂ and PM₁₀ that were measured in the Sant Antoni superblock before and after the intervention. The study discovered that NO₂ and PM₁₀ concentrations in the area dropped after the pacification intervention. The evaluation of the influence on pollution levels reveals a significant and statistically significant reduction in NO₂ levels of 14.6 g/m³, i.e., a 25% reduction, from the pre-intervention period. a drop in PM₁₀ particles is also seen (4.1 g/m³), which is 17% lower compared to the pre-intervention period.

Environmental Assessment-Acoustic Quality: The Department of Environmental Assessment and Management of Barcelona City Council has provided the noise statistics for Sant Antoni before and after the intervention period. According to the findings, the average daytime noise dropped by 3.5 decibels, or 5.2%, in the months after the intervention. Nighttime noise levels fluctuated from month to month, overall remaining at similar levels as pre-intervention levels.

Individual Assessment-Air Quality and Noise: A qualitative assessment was also conducted in Sant Antoni using ethnographic guerrillas. The neighbors in this instance had a very favorable opinion of the superblocks. Because there are fewer cars around, there is less noise, which results in quieter surroundings and better sleep, as well as less pollution.

Results in Poblenou:

Using focus groups, a qualitative analysis of the Poblenou superblock was conducted. Participants included young people, adults with children under 10 years old, adults without dependent children, elderly people, superblock employees, and women. There is general agreement across all categories of the population that the **number of motor vehicles has decreased**, which suggests that pollution has decreased, and air quality has improved. It also emphasizes the advantages of reduced noise pollution. Young people and employees, for example, may experience highly beneficial health outcomes from the superblock, but **other groups may experience poor health effects as a result of the increased pollution in the streets surrounding the superblock.**

Survey of the use of public spaces:

A survey is conducted in the cities where the intervention was implemented to evaluate the quality of public places and to understand how people interact with the public spaces since the presence of high-quality public spaces in communities can be related to well-being.

Horta:

According to a survey conducted in Horta, 25% of people traveled by the intervening area every day, and 90% of males and 85% of women visited there at least once a week. Only approximately 6% used it for physical activity, while more than 50% used it for walking or shopping.

Sant Antoni:

In the instance of Sant Antoni, both quantitative and qualitative evaluations of the use of spaces were conducted. Quantitatively, the profiles of use of space by people were counted and qualitatively ethnographic guerrillas were carried out on people who used the superblock.

During the survey, it was found that adults, **both men and women, used the superblock most frequently** around noon and in the late afternoon or evening, mostly for walking. The older population, including both men and women, was the second most prevalent

age group to use the Sant Antoni superblock. 2% of women and 6% of men were engaged in vigorous activity, and 94 and 89 percent of people were walking, respectively.

Poblenou:

In Poblenou, discussion groups were organized with a variety of groups, including elderly people, teenagers who study in the superblock, persons who work in or nearby the superblock, and a group made up solely of women.

All the groups agreed that families with children use the superblocks most frequently as children's play areas, and working people frequent them to eat or when the day ends. The other collectives use it above all in passing. **The majority of young people believe it is an area that was not created for them. The elderly people, however, note that they don't use the superblock and that it feels like a lonely place to them.** There is general agreement in terms of mobility that there are fewer motorized vehicles now, which has a good impact on mobility. **The elderly believe that the superblock has a detrimental impact on mobility because of changes to the public transportation network or challenges in getting into specific locations, including the Primary Healthcare Center.** Additionally, as was already indicated, some groups claim that traffic could have been diverted to other streets.

Results on Well-being and social interaction:

Horta:

835 respondents were obtained in a survey conducted before and after the intervention. Of these, 55% of the men and 45% of the women believed that **well-being on the streets was increased**. More than 60% of both men and women said **walking comfort had improved**, while almost 75% of men and 70% of women thought **stroller accessibility had improved**.

Sant Antoni:

It is found that the area is currently regarded as a wonderful place for the neighbors to pass and be quiet, comfortably, and safely. In this regard, the public space is made to

happen with more pedestrians and is now deemed to be more "full of life" and "more neighborhood" due to the reduction of cars and the presence of urban furniture. It is a place where you are encouraged to be. People can experience silence, safety, and comfort through a variety of things. As previously indicated, the absence of cars results in less noise, and this gives greater peace and quiet and better sleep. **All of this has effects on mental health, such as the impression of better security and serenity.** Even though there are more or less heightened levels of cars present, people with minors may feel this is a false sense of security. **Socialization is favored by the fact that there is less pollution and more room to be outside.**

Poblenou

Among individuals without dependent children, **stress levels were found to be lower** and the environment to be calmer. However, the superblock has no health effects on the elderly. As for the workers, the superblock's open floor plan encourages walking and offers tranquility, implying an improvement in mental health. In the case of women, there have been some discussions about the possibility of an impact on the streets surrounding the superblocks because the space encourages neighborly engagement, promoting relationships and social networks. Also, some women mention the area as deserted and perceive insecurity.

In this chapter the policy's impact on social, economic, and environmental dimensions, as well as its effects on walkability and its relationship with housing prices and immigrant integration were explored. Additionally, the current exclusion factors for the elderly and disabled in urban contexts, existing methods to evaluate the accessibility were identified. Through the literature review, we have also identified a list of cities that are implementing this policy, impact evaluation of similar policies, and the beneficiaries of 15-minute city policy. Overall, the analysis highlights the complex interconnection between various factors in shaping the success of the 15-minute city policy. Various factors that were analyzed are interconnected in several ways. For example, the walkability of a city is closely tied to its social, economic, and environmental dimensions. Walkable neighborhoods can improve public health, reduce transportation costs, and create a sense of community. Additionally, walkability can impact housing prices, making neighborhoods more desirable and driving up prices. However, this can also lead to gentrification and exclusion of lower-income residents. Immigrant integration can also

be impacted by walkability, as neighborhoods that are more walkable may facilitate social interactions and connections.

As we have seen throughout this chapter, scholars have put forward both the advantages and disadvantages of the 15-minute city policy. The advantages include the favorable effects on social, economic, and environmental factors that the 15-minute city will generate, as well as the increased social capital and cohesion that will result from the policy's emphasis on walkability. And the drawbacks, such as segregation and the growing housing prices as a result of walkability. However, there isn't enough evidence to say whether the policy actually increases inequality by only benefiting city center residents or whether it decreases inequality by also benefiting those who live outside the city center. Furthermore, despite the extensive policy rhetoric around the 15-minute city, there has been little discussion of how older people, age-friendly surroundings, and social inclusion fit into this agenda. Moreover, one of the key pillars of the 15-minute city policy is diversity, both in terms of people and culture. However, upon further exploration of the literature, it is clear that there has been little mention of strategies aimed at boosting immigrant integration as a means of achieving this diversity. Furthermore, research has demonstrated that walkability can help to build social capital, which in turn can facilitate the assimilation of immigrants into their new communities. therefore, a 15-minute city policy could serve as a powerful tool for encouraging immigrant integration, while also promoting greater diversity and social cohesion in urban areas. However, despite this, no research has specifically examined how the policy affects immigrants who live in cities. Also, there are no studies in the literature that concentrate on the context of Milan and analyze how inclusive the policy is by taking everyone into account since every city adopts its own method of executing the policy based on the city's context.

As we can see from the literature review, the 15-minute city urban policy gave less attention to the social and economic aspects of sustainability and focused more on the environmental side. To accomplish decarbonization, the primary goal is to limit the use of cars. In most cities, the primary initiatives include expanding bicycle lanes, making pedestrian space larger, and local micro markets focusing on minimizing the use of private cars, however, they neglected to consider how the excluded areas will meet their

needs in 15 minutes. While others can satisfy their needs within 15 minutes by walking or cycling, people with disabilities and the elderly population should also be able to satisfy their needs within 15 minutes. Whether it be medical attention, care services, etc.

3 Research questions:

In the previous chapter, some significant gaps in the literature regarding the 15-minute city policy were identified. Firstly, there is a lack of evidence on whether this policy will contribute to the reduction of the socio-economic disparities between the rich and poor. Secondly, the literature provides no clear explanation of how vulnerable populations, such as the elderly and disabled, will benefit from this policy. Lastly, there is no consensus on how the 15-minute city policy will facilitate immigrant integration. These gaps in the literature highlight the need for further investigation into the potential benefits and drawbacks of the 15-minute city policy. The gaps identified in the literature regarding the 15-minute city policy have been instrumental in the formulation of research questions for this thesis.

- 1. Could the implementation of the "15-minute city" policy potentially contribute to solve spatial inequalities in cities, and reduce the gap between the rich and the poor?**

Generally, economic inequality is greater in urban areas than in rural areas. The Gini coefficient of income inequality is higher in urban areas than in rural areas in 36 out of 42 countries (World Social Report, 2020) *Inequality in a rapidly changing world*). Larger cities are generally richer but more unequal than smaller cities. Therefore, it's important to consider if urban policies like the 15-minute city will help to narrow or exacerbate the gap between the rich and the poor before putting them into practice.

In the article *MATTERS OF SCALE: THE ILLUSION OF THE 15-MINUTE CITY*, Peverini & Chiaro, (2020) argue that this approach can never be equitable for all people and would exacerbate inequality. They mentioned that an important question is omitted from the policy's explanation. To put it another way, urban dynamics occur across considerably larger time and space than the 15-minute circle. So, for whom will the city of 15 minutes be? On the other side, who will still live in the city of the hour, the two hours, and the three hours? Housing costs, both for purchases and rentals, were greater in the central municipalities than in the outer ones. Another concern was raised by author Easton (2022)

in an article in *tibbalds*. He mentioned that the Paris En Commun strategy is only being applied to the inner ring area of the city, which is primarily inhabited by wealthier Parisians and not in the suburbs. Therefore, this could exacerbate the disparities between the rich and the poor. There is also another concern that the 15-minute city concept could accelerate gentrification. Gentrification is more likely to take place in high-density locations because "proximity-related" benefits become attractive to high-income households, says Pendall and Caruthers (2003, p. 527). Therefore, FMC neighborhoods would likely become more attractive as a result of the addition of local amenities, which would raise housing costs. As a result, populations with middle- and low-income levels will be pushed to move to outer municipalities where housing costs are cheaper.

Even though a poor neighborhood may have access to healthcare, there are not enough facilities and doctors are frequently in short supply. and schools lack the supplies and trained teachers needed to guarantee equal access to education. Additionally, there aren't many work opportunities in suburbs. Peverini & Chiaro (2020) and Whittle (2020) draw attention to the fact that not all urban residents can or do live near the place where they work because of issues with affordability brought about by land markets, where neighborhoods are chosen based on one's ability to pay for a home rather than on one's need (Dunning et al., 2021), resulting in a mismatch between housing and employment (Boussauw et al., 2010). As a result, individuals must sustain frequent travel in order to get high-quality healthcare, education, and employment in key metropolitan centers. Therefore, the focus of this question will be on whether the FMC concept will actually make the gap between the rich and the poor wider.

2. How does diversity, as one of the four pillars of the 15-minute city concept, affect the integration of immigrants and refugees into urban communities?

The role of diversity in the 15-minute city concept is twofold (i) the requirement for mixed-use neighborhoods, which are essential in offering a healthy mixture of residential, business, and entertainment components; and (ii) diversity in culture and people. The second aspect of diversity that would make those social functions even more thriving is neighborhoods that accommodate and encourage diverse cultures from different backgrounds (Moreno et al. 2021).

Promoting diversity also aids in fostering peaceful coexistence and lowers instances of hostility and anxiety, which in turn worsen inequality and insecurity (Lewis et al. 2018; Natalina Carrà 2016). However, in cities like Paris, immigrants, and refugees tend to live in clusters in more segregated neighborhoods away from the city. The public still perceives the public housing estates, which are scattered throughout numerous suburbs, negatively, labeling them as "immigrant-dominated slums" (Faleh et al., 2019). "The strong focus on spatial proximity is mainly criticized because it promotes segregation and isolation of neighborhoods," says Prof. Edward Glaeser from Harvard University, among others, at the digital LSE event "Urban Age Debate: Localising Transport,". In addition, despite the fact that some suburban areas of Paris are rather wealthy in comparison to the city center, the 15-minute city, as it is now designed, could exacerbate the territorial inequality and socioeconomic disparities already present in the area by segregating immigrants from the natives. Also, if the "15-minute city policy" is not accompanied by measures to address the extreme levels of socio-spatial segregation and inequality, risks of increasing segregation and isolation of neighborhoods exist.

Even though problems with racial and social segregation exist in cities like Paris, no strategy or program to address this problem is mentioned. Furthermore, While the proponents in the literature only mentioned design principles like density and diversity, no detailed guidelines are being made to promote diversity in order to achieve the 15-minute city. Therefore, the focus of this question will be on the extent to which the diversity pillar is emphasized in policy by various cities to ensure that immigrants and refugees are benefited and assimilated into the local culture. And if they implement any measures to overcome and avoid the racial segregation that hinders the integration of immigrants and refugees.

3. How might the 15-minute city policy, with its emphasis on speed, influence the accessibility to essential amenities for the most vulnerable groups, such as the elderly or those with disabilities?

Persons with disabilities make up nearly 15 percent of the global population, and in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), that number is nearly 20 percent. Even though more than half of all individuals with disabilities reside in cities, our cities rarely take mobility demands across the whole range of people's abilities into consideration (Artieda et al. 2022). In addition, the author argues that most cities are planned with the convenience of those in motor vehicles in mind rather than those who prefer to travel by foot, bicycle, or public transportation. Within this context, it's clear that cities need to reframe whom they are planning for. Interior architect and designer Dima Stouhi argue in her article titled "Our Cities are not Designed for the Disabled" urban planners are designing the cities according to time, and do not consider function or needs. The city of 15 minutes might vary greatly between generations. How much farther can an elderly person travel in 15 minutes compared to a teenager? Therefore, all cities should take into account people with disabilities and elderly people when examining various mobility strategies.

Another criticism of the 15-minute city is that it ignores the transportation requirements of disabled people who cannot afford to reside in affluent districts. The Disability Mobility Initiative director Anna Zivarts interviewed city dwellers who are unable to drive. The respondents discussed how frequently people had to choose between spending more money to live closer to transit and services and living in areas they could more easily afford but required them to depend on family and friends or charity rides for transportation. Additionally, since not all persons with disabilities can afford to live in cities with excellent amenities, they must sacrifice their comfort in order to maintain their financial security. Moreover, two priorities emerged through her research: First, accessibility to fixed-route transit should be a priority for people with mobility disabilities everywhere in the world, not just in dense, expensive cities. Secondly, creating a secure and accessible pedestrian infrastructure that enables secure linkages to public transportation. It is nearly impossible for people with disabilities to reach their transit at

the same time or with the same efficiency as a person who is able-bodied due to the lack of sidewalk ramps or accessible pedestrian signals.

Low-traffic neighborhoods and protected bike lanes have been rapidly implemented in the UK, resulting in a rise in walking and cycling and a decrease in the usage of motor vehicles. In the UK, the "Transport for All" assessment raised concerns about the exclusion of disabled persons during the quick deployment of low-traffic neighborhoods. According to the Transport for all study, many disabled persons felt a significant sense of injustice and unfairness at LTN measures, because there is such a marked lack of alternative possibilities for transit. Of the 78 disabled people and caregivers whose interview responses were examined, 77% of them reported longer travel times as a result of the implementation of a Low traffic neighborhood. Therefore, when establishing or designing a mobility strategy, urban planners and policymakers should consider the requirements of the elderly and disabled and ensure that everyone in the community has equal access to all services.

Hence, this question focuses on whether and how cities handle the socioeconomic disparity inside the city to ensure accessibility for all people, particularly disadvantaged populations. Since every city has a unique local environment, many experts opined that in order to provide equal services to all city residents, planners and policymakers should not adopt the concept without considering the context-specific conditions of cities. Each city's unique characteristics should be duly considered when planning 15-minute cities and place-based policy interventions are also necessary.

4 Methodology

The following set of methodologies are used in an effort to address the research questions and also bridge any significant gaps that surfaced during the extensive literature review conducted prior to this study. With the ultimate objective of producing insightful and significant findings.

Firstly, a detailed literature review was conducted in the previous chapter in order to fully understand how the 15-minute city policy works. This involved an extensive search of various sources including grey literature, journals, and result evaluation reports from other cities that have already implemented this policy. The main goal of this literature review was to comprehend the numerous advantages of the policy in terms of social, economic, and environmental benefits, as well as the potential drawbacks of the policy. Additionally, the review sought to understand the beneficiaries of the 15-minute city policy. Moreover, in order to gain insight into the potential impact of 15-minute city policy, an impact analysis report of a similar strategy implemented in Barcelona was included. This report was released by the Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona and was found through internet research. In order to ensure that the literature review was comprehensive, all relevant documents were sourced from both Google Scholar and Scopus, two of the most dependable academic search engines accessible.

After that, an empirical case study was conducted to examine the social inclusion of Milan's 15-minute city policy. Case study analysis is a useful method for understanding the implementation of urban policies, as it allows for an in-depth examination of specific cases and their contextual factors. According to Marcussen and Olsen (2014), case studies can provide insights into the actual practices and experiences" of policy implementation and allow for a fine-grained analysis of the interplay between contextual factors and policy outcomes. By examining specific cases, we can identify the factors that facilitate or hinder successful policy implementation and develop a nuanced understanding of the complex and dynamic nature of urban policy processes. The case study is primarily based on data from secondary sources, such as academic literature, reports, media, and the municipality's official website. The documents published on the Comune di Milano's official website have been mainly utilized to comprehend how the policy works in Milan.

The different interventions that are a part of the 15-minute city urban policy have been identified by referring to several documents posted on the municipality website. The location where the projects are going to be implemented and additional information about the projects were then determined using the ProduzionidalBasso website which is a platform for crowdfunding.

4.1 Analysis of characteristics of neighborhoods where the interventions are implemented:

The neighborhood's characteristics were examined in terms of various factors in order to identify the major issues that the neighborhood where the project is being carried out is experiencing. By doing so, we will be able to determine whether the projects will solve the problems that already exist in the neighborhood. To determine the neighborhood's characteristics, a number of variables were considered, including the ones listed below.

1. Unhealthy production activities
2. Number of schools
3. Presence of childcare services
4. Number of pharmacies
5. Presence of shops with home delivery options
6. Services for foreigners.
7. Number of libraries.
8. Demographic indexes.

All the information was gathered from the municipality's official geoportale website ([link](#)). The demographics of the neighborhoods where the project is being implemented were gathered from a document titled "Milano e i suoi quartieri anno 2020" that was published on the official website of the Milan municipality ([link](#)). The demographics of each neighborhood were examined to determine the predominant age groups that live in each neighborhood and whether the project being implemented will be beneficial to all age groups there.

Unhealthy production activities:

Harmful production operations are any industrial or manufacturing processes that release vapors, gases, or other unwholesome fumes, or that have the potential to be

equally hazardous to the public's health and to the environment. By Referring to the geoportal map we can see all first- and second-class unhealthy activities that are now occurring or have stopped inside the Milanese municipal region. According to the Ministerial Decree of September 5, 1994, any craft or industrial operations are categorized as harmful activities depending on the chemical substances, products, and materials involved in the industrial process. The activities are further classified into two types:

First-class: those that must be kept away from populated areas unless the owner can prove that their activity doesn't harm residents' health.

Second class: those that could exist in an urban setting but call for extra security measures to protect the community.

Number of schools:

The presence of schools can be recognized as a significant aspect of the growth and development of the local community. Schools play a significant role in the social and intellectual development of children. hence the number of public schools in various neighborhoods was taken into consideration while determining the characteristics. When the neighborhoods lack adequate schools, Families with the financial means leave their neighborhoods and migrate to more affluent parts of the city. such processes of realignment and concentration of the population are known as segregation. The result of this segregation is a concentration of problem factors in local neighborhoods (Baur, 2013).

Presence of childcare services:

The availability of childcare services (0–6 years) in each neighborhood was plotted. These services include municipal nurseries, contract nurseries, municipal nursery schools, early childhood centers, toy libraries, and spring break times for families.

Presence of shops with home delivery options:

In each neighborhood, a map of the shops that offer home delivery was plotted. these services include shopping delivery, meals, and pet food. At Milan, There are more than 370 open businesses, ranging from grocery stores to pharmacies, that provide residents of the communities home delivery services. At times of need, the town assists neighborhood small businesses in offering home delivery services. Three goals were

pursued by the project: the first was to provide each neighborhood with a list of small businesses open and offering home delivery, especially for the elderly, lonely, and ill; the second was to minimize crowds and shorten lines at large retailers; and the third, and possibly most significant goal, was to value neighborhood trade as a means of territorial defense and neighborhood wealth.

Services for foreigners.

A hackathon to improve services for migrants was launched in Milan under the name SERVICES4MIGRANTS. The establishment of a technical assistance and guide service for migrants living in the city is the focus of the Services4MIgrants hackathon. The Municipality of Milan is dedicated to giving immigrants the knowledge they need to enable smooth access to services; for the more complex ones, it has produced printed guides.

Number of libraries.

According to UNESCO, the presence of libraries in a community is crucial because they serve as venues for intergenerational learning, the development of digital skills, the promotion of cultural heritage, social inclusion, environmental and physical education, as well as health promotion. Also, Libraries are community hubs. They connect people to information and connect people to people.

Demographic indexes:

Demographic indices including dependence index, average age, and percentage of young people and persons over 65 were taken into account in order to comprehend the basics of the neighborhood characteristics.

Using these above-mentioned factors, the characteristics of all of the neighborhood where the project is being implemented are noted and compiled into a table which can be found in the appendix section.

Example: Neighborhood- Corvetto

In order to provide a detailed demonstration of how the data for each factor was collected from the geoportal website for the neighborhoods, an example of the data for the neighborhood Corvetto is shown below.

Overview: Corvetto is a neighborhood in Milan's Municipio 4 and is situated in the city's southeast. The neighborhood's demographic features are as follows:

Dependence Index- 55.8

Average age Index- 45.7

Percentage of young people adults 15-34- 20.8

Percentage of foreigners- 26.7

Unhealthy production activities:

- | | | | |
|---|--------------------------|---|---------------------------|
| | Cessate di 1° classe |
| | Cessate di 2° classe |
| | Cessate di 1° e 2° classe |

Figure 6: Locations of unhealthy production activities

Number of schools:

Kindergartens

primary schools

Lower secondary school

Figure 7: Locations of school

Presence of childcare services

Childhood services

ServicesChildhood

- EARLY CHILDHOOD CENTER
- TOYS LIBRARY
- MUNICIPAL NURSERIES
- CONTRACT NURSERIES
- MUNICIPAL NURSERY SCHOOLS
- SPRING SECTIONS
- TIME FOR FAMILIES

Services For foreigners

Post_Offices_Milan

Headquarters_Trade

Unions_and_Patronati_Comune_Milan

Headquarters_Trade

Unions_and_Patronati_Province_Milan

Offices_for_Eligibility_Abitative

Offices_for_Eligibility_Abitative

Schools Italian

Embassies

Consulates

Lottomatica

Figure 10: Location of services for foreigners

Number of pharmacies:

Figure 11: location of pharmacies

Presence of shops with home delivery options

- Grocery - Minimarket - Food - Frozen Products
- Others
- Bar - Restaurant - Cafeteria – Pizzeria
- Fish shop
- Bakery - Sweets - Focacceria
- Stationery and office supplies - Games and toys - Bookshops – Newsstand

Figure 12: Location of shops with delivery options

Likewise, the characteristics for each neighborhood where the project is being implemented were analyzed and compiled into an excel file.

4.2 Selection of Vulnerable neighborhoods:

Following the identification of the actions and projects that are being carried out or have already been implemented in various neighborhoods, the vulnerable neighborhoods in Milan were identified. The vulnerable neighborhoods were then selected in order to determine which areas needed the most attention, to discover whether interventions were distributed fairly, and to evaluate the degree of inclusion during the implementation of the policy. Vulnerable neighborhoods that require attention were selected based on a number of indicators. These indicators, which can be referred to as risk indicators since they evaluate the neighborhood's risk, are given below:

- high dependency rate.
- percentage of the population over 65 who lives alone.
- High unemployment rate
- Immigrants at risk of exclusion,
- low-income residents
- high crime rate.
- Percentage of population leaving school early.

These data were derived from Milan's 2011 census report, which was made available on the municipality's official website.

High dependency rate- This indicator measures how many Milanese are under 14 years old and over 64 years old, considered inactive age for every 100 between 15 and 64 years in age potentially active. The indicator evaluates the sustainability of the structure demographic of Milan in terms of age and, indirectly, the sustainability of welfare citizens. Larger values indicate greater structural dependence of demographic groups potentially inactive versus active ones, therefore more difficult situations. A high dependency ratio is supposedly a sign of the dependency burden on the working population because it is assumed that the economically active portion of the population will need to pay for the health, education, pension, and social security benefits of the non-working population, either directly through family support mechanisms or indirectly through taxation. Future growth, savings, consumption, taxation, and retirement will all suffer as a result of rising dependency ratios (Ingham et al., 2009).

Percentage of the population over 65 who lives alone- This metric measures What proportion of Milanese older than 65 years old live alone. The indicator analyzes the presence of potentially serious problems with the isolation of the elderly and applies to families with only one member over 65. These people are more prone to issues including medical emergencies, social isolation, heightened anxiety and depressive symptoms, malnutrition, etc.

High unemployment rate: This indicator measures how many Milanese aged 15 or older who are actively seeking jobs make up the total population of Milanese. The indicator shows the percentage of the workforce that is either looking for their first job or seeking new employment as a result of losing their current position. As a result, we can assess the excess labor supply versus the demand as indicated by the economic system. It is one of the primary cycle indicators for the local economy.

Neighborhoods with the most immigrants: The indicator shows how many residents are foreign-born as a percentage of all residents. This comprises both foreigners and foreigners who have registered in the registry office as well as foreign parents who have had children born in Italy. Foreigners who have obtained Italian citizenship are excluded from this list.

Neighborhoods with highest school dropouts: The indicator measures how many Milanese between the ages of 15 and 19 do not have a high school diploma. Young people who have not finished their required education have a higher risk of being excluded from society and the workforce.

Neighborhoods with a high percentage of students who don't have a diploma: The indicator measures the proportion of youth between the ages of 15 and 24 who drop out of school before earning a secondary school diploma or higher. A higher level of education typically ensures young people greater opportunities to enter the labor market effectively and significant social recognition.

High crime rate: Citizens published a number of neighborhoods online based on various crimes including robbery, drug peddling, frequent clashes, etc. The neighborhoods that

are listed online correspond to areas with higher rates of unemployment, higher rates of dropouts, areas where residents live in smaller homes, etc.

Please refer to the appendix section for a list of the neighborhoods under each variable. The neighborhoods that require more attention were determined by analyzing whether a neighborhood appears on two or more of the aforementioned lists.

4.3 Mapping and comparisons:

After conducting extensive research on the interventions included in the 15-minute city policy and identifying the vulnerable neighborhoods in Milan, a mapping exercise was conducted using the Comune di Milano's geoportal website. The purpose of this exercise was to graphically represent the neighborhoods where the projects were being implemented and the ones that were identified as vulnerable. By marking these neighborhoods on a map of the Milan municipality, it was possible to gain a deeper understanding of the level of social inclusion and determine whether the projects were being implemented in the vulnerable neighborhoods as well. This mapping exercise helped to provide a more comprehensive and insightful view of the distribution of the interventions and how they could be targeted to enhance social inclusion and promote equitable development. Overall, the mapping of these neighborhoods contributed significantly to the development of actionable insights and recommendations to enhance the effectiveness of the 15-minute city policy in Milan.

After conducting the mapping exercise, it was possible to identify several vulnerable neighborhoods that were not receiving any interventions or support. It was crucial to note these areas as they are often the most overlooked and underserved communities. Once these neighborhoods were identified, the next step was to identify the various risk factors associated with them. These risk factors could include high unemployment rates, high school dropout rates, or a large population of immigrants. By identifying these factors, it was possible to gain valuable insights into the possible barriers that these neighborhoods face when it comes to participating in the policy-making process. It is essential to understand the underlying issues and challenges faced by these communities to ensure that they are not left behind and have equal opportunities to participate in the

decision-making processes that affect their lives. By addressing these barriers and challenges, we can create a more inclusive and equitable society for all.

Furthermore, a thorough comparison between the needs of the neighborhoods where the projects are implemented and the type of projects, they received was conducted with great detail. To ensure the accuracy of this comparison, a detailed analysis of the neighborhood characteristics was conducted, as previously described. This analysis allowed for a better understanding of the problems the neighborhoods are currently facing. For instance, the neighborhoods with a high elderly population living alone might have fewer shops offering home delivery options or pharmacies. Similarly, neighborhoods with a significantly younger immigrant population might lack public schools nearby. By conducting such comparisons, we were able to identify the urgent needs of the neighborhood and compare them with the type of intervention to determine if the intervention effectively addresses the problems faced by the community. This approach helped us to ensure that the projects implemented were tailored to meet the specific needs of the neighborhood and to achieve the desired outcomes.

After a thorough examination of Milan's policy execution, there are several important insights that can be gained. By comparing the vulnerable neighborhoods with those in which the projects are being implemented it is possible to gain valuable information about the even distribution of projects and the level of inclusiveness that is being achieved. Additionally, it can shed light on the crucial question of "where the problems are and where the solutions are" with great clarity. Another key insight that has emerged from this analysis is that by comparing the type of intervention with the characteristics of the neighborhoods, it is possible to gain a deeper understanding of whether the projects are designed to address the urgent problems of the community. This kind of analysis can provide information to ensure that the projects are effective and that they have a positive impact on the lives of the people who live in these neighborhoods.

5 15-minute city policy in Milan

In this chapter, the case study of Milan is introduced, highlighting the strategy in which the Milan municipality introduced the 15-minute city approach. The chapter explains the various strategies and actions taken by the Milan '2020 adaptation strategy' to achieve this goal, including making essential services and amenities available within a 15-minute walk or bike ride for residents. Furthermore, the chapter explains the call for social impact investments, known as mi15, which aimed to promote projects that could have a positive social impact on the community. The criteria used to select projects as part of the mi15 call were also explained.

The municipality of Milan proposed its "**2020 Adaptation Strategy**" in May 2020 as a plan to recover from the COVID-19 impact. The municipality wants to develop strategies to deal with what is known as "Phase 2," which is characterized by the radical changes in lifestyles brought on by sanitary restrictions, social segregation, and proximity restrictions. The main objective of the adaptation strategy is to assist the city in recovering from COVID-19's consequences and strengthening its resilience. The adaptation strategy is seen as a national recovery and resilience program and has offered several recommendations, including self-sufficient neighborhoods and environmentally friendly transportation, to help the city recover from COVID-19. The 2020 adaptation strategy specifically highlighted the construction of the 15-minute neighborhoods in the plan's "**services and neighborhood**" section. The objective is to bring all necessary services within a 15-minute walkable distance by enhancing public services from a proximity perspective, developing territorial healthcare services, favoring home delivery and shipping, etc. The strategy has taken into account a variety of population targets, including age, sanitary conditions and health, employment position, and financial situation. The goal was to quickly restore normalcy, but it was also important to prepare the population for a "new normal" by implementing a period of "post-lockdown containment". Furthermore, the proposed plan's objectives are related to parts of the SDGs, including SDGs 3 (good health and well-being), 10 (reduced inequalities), 11 (sustainable cities and communities), 8 (decent work and economic growth), and 13 (climate action). Therefore, this strategy is viewed as a comprehensive solution to

mitigate the effects of COVID-19 as well as a way to compact climate change and create resilient cities.

5.1 Strategies, actions, and projects in Milan's 2020 adaptation strategy:

- **Rhythms and timing-** The goal is to increase flexibility through the extension of timetables for businesses, restaurants, and leisure activities; by the provision of incentives for the movement of vehicles and people during "flat" hours; Change school entry and exit times to relieve congestion in the transportation network, and work with large and medium-sized businesses to develop regulations that enable remote work and desynchronize work schedules to make it easier for slow-moving people to get around.
- **Mobility-** The main objective is to reduce movements and diversify the supply of mobility. This policy's goal is to reduce movements while diversifying the mobility options available. It encourages walking, the usage of motorbikes and electric scooters, and the implementation and extension of 30 km/h zones. Additionally, this strategy has been used to implement open street programs ("Strade Aperte"). Also, 35 new kilometers of cycling lanes are about to be built under the open street program, along with wider sidewalks and temporary pedestrianization of neighborhoods.
- **Public space and well-being-** This strategy aims to reclaim space for outdoor sporting activity and exercises. Additionally, the Open Squares project ("Piazze Aperte") will be created in every neighborhood in support of pedestrians, particularly in locations close to services and educational institutions as well as in places with fewer green spaces, to encourage outdoor play and physical activity. The project's goal is to reestablish public space as the focal point of the community and the lives of its inhabitants.
- **Digital Services:** The strategy's objectives include enhancing online municipal library services, accelerating the development of digital services for citizens, promoting online cultural initiatives, boosting online learning opportunities, etc.

- **Services and neighborhoods-** the main objective of this method is to make everything accessible within a 15-minute walk. moreover, the municipality plans to establish neighborhood clinics in partnership with the Lombardy Region administration, starting from low-income, densely populated districts and regions with a larger concentration of senior citizens. In addition to that, it also has plans to promote online shopping and delivery of groceries and other goods, giving priority to elderly people, improving local commercial networks, and assisting neighborhood companies.
- **Culture-** This plan aims to spread culture through the redesign of museums and other indoor cultural venues while taking into account the need for physical distancing; Improving the proximity of cultural services; offering incentives for the planning of limited-capacity events and initiatives that may be repeated in other local neighborhoods of the city, etc.
- **Economic activities-** The strategy intends to support social innovation and start-ups that combine commercial and nonprofit goals while fostering neighborhood togetherness. additionally, it intends to offer assistance for individuals and small businesses through social credit financing services, layoff anticipation, and social services for location.
- **Infrastructures, housing, and public works-** To initiate extensive maintenance and redevelopment projects on current real estate assets, both public and private, along with energy-saving initiatives, environmental reconstruction, and improved home comfort, in an effort to stimulate the recovery of the construction sector's recovery. Additionally, it encourages buildings' dual usage. for instance, "Scuole aperte,"(Open Schools) promotes the use of school buildings to welcome visitors and to provide educational programs in their green spaces, especially during the summer months.
- **Collaboration and assistance-** to Support collaborative economic systems realized with a bottom-up approach and to strengthen the civil protection system and the management of volunteers. Also, an initiative called Milano Aiuta - Milano Does Help has also been implemented. The objective is to Keep and improve some of

the services that Milano Aiuta launched, particularly those that are related to home support, collaborative services, and grocery delivery.

5.2 Mi15: A new call for social impact investments:

The Municipality of Milan launched a new tender called "Mi15" that encourages investments in social impact by for-profit and nonprofit organizations. The goal is to activate or enhance spaces and services in neighborhoods to create the "15-minute city". The primary goal of the project proposals must be the creation or improvement of areas, services, or activities that have a social impact, which is currently missing or insufficient in the area where they operate and be able to improve residents' quality of life. Furthermore, this initiative is part of a larger Civil Economy support program in the neighborhoods funded with European funds for the REACT-EU recovery under the PON Metro Milano 2014 2020, which also includes the " La Scuola dei Quartieri 2022" and the " Crowdfunding Civico 2022."

La Scuola dei Quartieri 2022- Under this initiative, the Municipality of Milan encourages groups of citizens to offer project suggestions that could have a good social impact in the areas of the city. The projects should be able to enhance the social, economic, or environmental well-being of the communities in which they operate. The municipality listed some potential project topic areas, including proximity services, social aggregation, care, well-being, commercial and creative activities with social impact, etc.

Crowdfunding Civico 2022- The call is aimed at non-profit organizations that want to suggest social and cultural innovation projects with a view of caring for communities and 15 minutes city.

5.3 Interventions in Milan

Milan Municipality undertakes several ambitious actions to support urban sustainable development. The "Milan 2020 adaption strategy" is being executed through a number of

initiatives. Its objective is to make key systems accessible within 15 minutes of walking distance in order to minimize movements and increase the neighborhood dimension. The Adaptation Plan focuses on a number of issues, but the importance is devoted to providing incentives for the revival of local production and the creation of new, short integrated production lines.

All these initiatives are connected in the integrated view of the New Urban Development Plan which aims at leading Milan towards 2030 by continuing the positive evolution of the city. Adopted in 2018, the main purposes of the plan are:

- promoting inclusive growth benefitting all neighborhoods and social groups,
- and combining development with the improvement of environmental conditions, quality of life, and the supply of urban green areas.

The Urban Development Plans intends to build a connected, metropolitan, and global city. In order to achieve this goal, urban planning will be strongly related to the development of mobility infrastructures, with the aim of having the majority of the population living and working at a short distance from a train or metro stop and also reducing dependence on private mobility. In the broad context of the "Milan2030" New Urban Development Plan, several pragmatical actions have been undertaken.

5.3.1 Other selected projects:

Numerous initiatives, innovative ideas, and proposals with a focus on taking care of neighborhoods and the "City of 15 Minutes Away" have been chosen by the Municipality of Milan to access civic crowdfunding. These initiatives are now available for citizen fundraising. Through the support of small enterprises, commercial endeavors, and initiatives, the objective is to take care of the communities and tangibly create a "city 15 minutes away." explains the economic development councilor. The chosen projects have 45 days to try and collect 40% of the needed resources. With non-repayable payments totaling up to 48,000 euros, the Municipality will contribute its part of the remaining financing, thanks to the European resources of PON Metro React Eu.

The 'Mi15' Notice calls for the proposal of investment ideas that meet the criteria listed below:

- **USEFUL** - able to provide favorable impacts for the neighborhood or a particular category of recipients.
- **DURABLE** - able to endure throughout time and maintain themselves on their own when the project is finished.
- **ACCESSIBLE** refers to costs, time, the lack of barriers for those with disabilities, or social and economic instability.

All chosen projects must go through crowdfunding and raise 40% of the money in order to receive the remaining 60% from the Milan municipality. All project-related information has been made available to the public via a number of channels in an effort to raise awareness of the initiative. All the chosen initiatives had succeeded in raising the required 40% of the money.

6 Results and Findings

6.1 Interventions in Milan

The 15-minute city urban policy interventions have been identified through various methods, as detailed in Chapter 6. The interventions have been categorized based on the stakeholders they target and are listed below. Each intervention includes a description of the project, the location of the neighborhood, and the expected impact it can have on the community.

6.1.1 Interventions focusing on all residents:

This category of interventions aims to benefit all residents by improving public spaces and promoting a healthier, more sustainable lifestyle. By prioritizing walkability and reducing car usage and encouraging the use of sustainable transportation these interventions aim to enhance the quality of life for everyone. Examples of these interventions include the creation of new public squares, the construction of dedicated cycle lanes, and other measures that give back public spaces to people. By encouraging socialization and reducing our carbon footprint, these interventions have the potential to create positive impacts both on our environment and our communities. Moreover, the open square and open street projects in Milan have also created opportunities for socialization and community building. They have become popular gathering places for people of all ages, providing spaces for public events, markets, and performances.

"Strade Aperte" project- The project comprises plans, initiatives, and resources for encouraging walking and cycling to guarantee measures of distance in urban travel and for sustainable mobility. The proposed initiatives align with the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan's existing predictions (PUMS). The main objectives of the Strategy are to add 35 kilometers of new cycling lanes by the end of the year, extend 30-kilometer speed limits, widen walkways, and temporarily convert some neighborhoods into pedestrian-only areas. Cycle pathways have been installed for 32,3 km since May 2020, and by the end of 2021, they should cover 61,7 km.

Locations

Figure 13: Map-Via Martiri Oscuri - A cycle lane Contraflow, delimited by a bollard.

Figure 14: Map-Isola district, Via Toce

Figure 15: Map-Porta Venezia-Lazzaretto district.

Figure 16: Map-Isola district, Via Minniti.

“Città 30” (30 km/h city):

The "Città 30" replaces the present 50 km/h speed restriction set by the Highway Code in all residential zones with a 30 km/h limit for around 60% of the entire urban road network.

Location- Via Rovereto.

Figure 17: Map- Via Rovereto

Piazze Aperte" project

The City of Milan is implementing this initiative Together with Bloomberg Associates, the National Association of City Transportation Officials (NACTO), and Global Designing Cities Initiatives. To improve the environment and the quality of life in the city, the open square project seeks to develop public spaces and make them community gathering places, expand pedestrian zones, and encourage sustainable means of transportation. It uses the tactical urbanism approach to bring public space back to the center of the neighborhood and the life of the inhabitants.

The outcome achieved from 2018:

- 27 new social spaces
- 20.000 m2 new pedestrian area
- 220 benches
- 250 potted plants
- 350 bicycle stations
- 50 tables (25 ping pong)
-

Aims of the Piazze Aperte program:

- To revitalize and remodel neighborhood streets and squares as hubs of social interaction and community gathering, reclaiming urban areas for the general public.
- To increase pedestrian and cycling safety through traffic-calming measures and pedestrianization, with a special emphasis on protecting young children, the elderly, and those with disabilities.
- To transform existing public spaces through low-cost high-impact street transformations before addressing permanent interventions.
- To promote community participation by fostering effective cooperation between citizens and the local government through the joint administration of community resources.

TACTICAL URBANISM MEASURES FROM 2018 TO 2021			
2018	2019	2020	2021
Piazza Dergano - 1	Piazzale Stazione Genova - 4	Piazzale Loreto - 17	Via De Nora - 35
Piazza Angilberto II - 2	Piazza Gasparri - 5	Via Pacini - 18	Piazza Torri Bianche - 36
Piazza San Luigi - 3	Via Spoleto / via Venini - 6	Via Laghetto - 19	Piazzale Bacone - 37
	Piazza Belloveso - 7	Via Toce - 20	Piazzetta SS Patroni - 38
	Piazzale Lavater - 8	Piazzale Ferrara - 21	
	Via Guido Reni - 9	Piazza Sicilia - 22	
	Piazzale Corvetto - 10	Via Monte Velino - 23	
	Piazzale Cooperazione - 11	Via Val Lagarina - 24	
	Via Rovereto / via Gilessa - 12	Piazza Minniti - 25	
	Via Abbiati - 13	Via Pontano - 26	
	Via Santa Rita da Cascia - 14	Piazzetta Capuano - 27	
	Via Gigante - 15	Piazzale Tripoli - 28	
	Piazza Alfieri - 16	Piazzale Fabio Chiesa - 29	
		Largo Balestra - 30	
		Piazzale Tirana - 31	
		Viale Monte Ceneri - 32	
		Via Pacinotti - 33	
		Via Quarti - 34	

Suggestions submitted in response to the Call for proposals applications "Piazze Aperte in ogni quartiere"

Pilot projects
Local initiative projects

Figure 18: Piazze Aperte program

As a result of this project, one in two Milanese citizens now has a square within 15 minutes (800 meters) from their home.

12

4

15

Figure 19: Locations of open squares project

Bookstop – Panchine letterarie- aims to create literary benches in bookstop where you can meet to read, borrow, buy, and discuss books, the bookstop also tells you the story of the area and the encounter between nature and the city and advises you on what to do on the weekend also it's a bench where you can find stories: meetings with the author, workshops, cultural events for all ages.

Expected results and impacts:

encourage socializing among people of various ages.

Location: borders of Parco Nord Milano.

6.1.2 Interventions focusing on teenagers.

There are several interventions that specifically target teenagers, aiming to promote their personal and mental well-being, foster creativity, and improve their education. These interventions take a multifaceted approach, incorporating a range of activities and programs that cater to the unique needs and interests of teenagers. One of the key components of these interventions is promoting creativity, which intends to have a positive impact on personal and well-being. To achieve this, there are initiatives in place that provide access to creative spaces and materials, as well as workshops and classes that allow teenagers to explore and express themselves through various art forms. In addition to promoting creativity, the interventions also focus on education and skills development. There are programs in place that provide academic support, mentoring, and guidance to help teenagers succeed in school and prepare for their future careers. By focusing on education and skills development, these interventions aim to improve the long-term prospects and opportunities available to teenagers in Milan. The impacts of these interventions on teenagers are expected to be significant. By providing access to creative spaces and educational programs, teenagers will have the opportunity to develop their skills and talents, express themselves, and find a sense of purpose and fulfillment. This, in turn, can lead to improvements in their mental and personal well-being, as well as their academic and professional success. Ultimately, these interventions have the potential to empower teenagers and contribute to the growth and development of the city

iGame al Galla- Youth, Aggregation, Music, and Events in the Spazio Indifesa Hub, designed for the Boys and Girls of the Neighborhood and the City, but Open to Families and Everyone Who Wants to See Gallaratese revive. The goal is to expand Spazio indifesa Hub so that it also serves as a hub for young people to interact, have fun, learn, express themselves, and collaborate.

Expected results and impacts:

- Foster creativity in young people.
- Promoting personal well-being

Location- Via Appennini, 50.

MEM-Out, per un'educazione della memoria in uscita- The proposal intends to launch a brand-new method of interaction between the public and the institution, in which the Memorial, from a place of welcome, becomes an active agent that encounters the territory, leaving its spaces. It aims to provide a widely accessible service for engaging and developing the stories that this location both preserves and communicates.

Location- Milano centrale

MI Barrio's- It aims to accompany teenagers in harmonious growth through art and culture and enhance the neighborhood and its meeting place by hosting various cultural events.

Expected results and impacts:

promoting art and culture through various events.

Location: Barona district

6.1.3 Interventions focusing on children:

This category of interventions focuses on children with the intention of providing them with a high-quality education, promoting their social integration, and assisting in the growth of their personalities. These interventions adopt a comprehensive strategy, including a range of initiatives and programs that are tailored to the particular requirements and passions of children. Inclusion in sports and education is one of the main goals of these programs. There are initiatives in place that provide access to sports

facilities, equipment, and coaching, with the aim of helping children develop their physical abilities and social skills. By participating in sports, children have the opportunity to interact with their peers, build confidence, and learn valuable life skills such as teamwork and sportsmanship. In addition to promoting social inclusion in sports, the interventions also focus on education and creative activities. There are programs in place that educate children about their rights and offer a range of creative educational activities that help them develop their personalities and express themselves. By focusing on education and creativity, these interventions aim to provide children with a well-rounded and fulfilling childhood experience. Also, children will have the opportunity to develop strong social skills, build friendships, and feel more connected to their communities.

Coach di quartiere 2023- The goal of the project is to reduce the distance between sporting events and children who cannot afford traditional sports financially and physically by moving closed gyms into public areas with free access. The goal is to recruit and educate young volunteers to serve as district coaches who, along with a trained educator, will be able to connect with these kids after school and spend the afternoon playing sports and having fun with them.

Expected results and impacts:

- Promote inclusion in sports.
- Encourage social integration.
- Enhance mental and physical health and therefore personal development.

Location- Milano Municipio 7

Il Parlamento dei bambini-

Since the majority of Milan's residents live in the suburbs, these areas will serve as a true testing ground for the development of an informed and integrated citizenry. Additionally, this project will foster communication between children and adults, promote good practices and habits in the neighborhood, and draw authorities' attention to a region that wants to grow and improve.

The Children's Parliament is a theatre workshop where youngsters may express their thoughts about the world and how they envision it to be in the future by writing and by

acting out in front of the public. Children are to be taught about their rights and the societal concerns that affect them.

Expected results and impacts:

- Development of the child's personality, talents, and abilities,
- Respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms will be fostered in children as a result of their sense of justice, fairness, and equality.
- Helps kids to recognize their individuality and power.

Location- Barona district

Campus creativo e naturalistico Corvetto- intends to offer a service with 8-hour activities a day for 30 children in the neighborhood, aged between 6 and 11. They will be creative activities with artists with proven educational experience, naturalistic activities in the Agroforest, and guided visits to local museums followed by workshops with the word. It will be A unique experience as it combines a family assistance service with creative and educational activities.

Expected results and impacts:

- Compact social inequalities among children from various ethnic backgrounds.
- Offer quality education.

Location: Corvetto district

6.1.4 Interventions focusing on Vulnerable populations:

This set of interventions focuses on the vulnerable population in Milan and aims to create a positive impact in their lives. These interventions focus specifically on low-income households, people with disabilities, and women victims of violence. By providing support to these communities through the provision of products or training and employment opportunities, Milan is addressing challenges like poverty and the various problems faced by vulnerable populations. This interventions are crucial in promoting social inclusion and ensuring that no one is left behind in the pursuit of sustainable development.

Adotta una gallina- By building a neighborhood chicken coop to house the chickens that will reside in the Agroforest, this project enables people to begin a regenerative micro supply chain. You can adopt a hen through the project, give her a name, visit her, and pick up her eggs right from the field in addition to adopting her. Families who are experiencing financial instability would benefit from the establishment of this community program. With a focus on those who experience higher social hardship, the goal is to foster socio-territorial coherence while addressing the issues with integration and participation of those who experience greater social hardship.

Expected results& impacts-

- Can enhance local micro-chain.
- Make healthier food available for people living in poverty.
- promote socio-territorial cohesion.
- transform abandoned and polluted green areas into agricultural forests.
- Improve health by promoting organic foods.

Location - Corvetto, Vigentino and Chiaravalle

Pasto Sospeso - A Milano l'inclusione sa di buono

The project aims to systematize neighborhood human capital development processes and build local ties within Milan's 4th district. The project Supports Families and Individuals with Fragility or at Risk of Social Exclusion by providing a Complete and Nutritionally Balanced Meal. This will improve the living conditions of many people and families in difficulty. The meals are prepared by young people with disabilities. As a result, this will simultaneously provide vulnerable citizen groups, young people with disabilities, and possibilities for social interaction and social cohesion with productive opportunities.

The organic raw materials at Km 0 are provided by the solidarity purchasing organization Alveare che dice si - Forlanini, transformed by the UNICA inclusive gastronomic laboratory of the La Nostra Comunità Association, and then distributed by volunteers of the Ancora Families Association, a local organization that assists families in Poverty.

Expected results and impacts:

- Reduced food waste.
- Reduce poverty.
- Inclusion of people with disabilities.

Location- Forlanini- Taliedo, Morsenchio, Forlanini, and Salomone districts.

La scherma per il benessere del corpo e della mente- Everyone can practice fencing at Accademia Scherma Milano, including those who are sighted, blind, or have other physical or mental disabilities, in a newly rebuilt gym with no physical obstacles.

Expected results and impacts:

- Promote inclusion in Sports.
- Promote the physical and mental health of people with disabilities.
- Establish interpersonal ties and build positive social relationships.

Location- Via Filippo Sasseti

La sartoria che cura- To offer free services including tailoring classes and a psychological support desk for women who have been the victims of abuse and violence.

Expected results and impacts:

- Improved mental health.
- Reduced rates of Re-Victimization.
- Economic empowerment.

Location: Dergano

6.1.5 Interventions focusing on young people.

There are several interventions in Milan that focus on the youth population which aims to provide job placement programs, therapy projects, and programs that promote inclusion and develop interpersonal skills. These interventions are designed to address the unique challenges that young people face in terms of entering the workforce, building

confidence, and developing social skills. The job placement programs aim to provide young people with the training and support they need to find meaningful employment, while the therapy projects focus on helping them regain self-confidence and improve their communication skills. The inclusion and interpersonal skills programs aim to foster a sense of belonging and connection within the community, which can have a positive impact on the mental health and overall well-being of young people. These interventions can have a positive impact on the youth population by providing job placement programs, young people will have access to the skills and resources they need to enter the workforce and build a sustainable career. This can help to reduce the high rates of youth unemployment and increase their economic independence. The therapy projects are expected to have a positive impact on mental health, as young people learn to overcome challenges and build their self-confidence. Additionally, the inclusion and interpersonal skills programs aim to help young people build strong social connections and develop the skills they need to succeed in both their personal and professional lives. Ultimately, these interventions have the potential to empower young people and contribute to the growth and development of the city of Milan.

Mare food academy- It establishes a training and job placement program for motivated young people in economically and socially precarious situations, giving them the chance to master a trade in the restaurant industry and rethink their future.

Expected results and impacts:

- Tackle youth unemployment problems.
- Job inclusion
- The reduced poverty rate among young people.

Locations- San Siro, Cascina Merlata, San Cristoforo, Rogoredo, Santa Giulia.

Radio Dynamo Milano- aims to implement Recreational Therapy projects for children and young people with disabilities and chronic diseases to regain self-confidence, overcome their fears, learn to listen to each other, and process their emotions. It involves children and teenagers in the creation of small radio programs during the sessions. Dynamo guests have fun drafting texts on topics proposed by the staff and broadcast live or record the radio formats that they themselves have prepared.

Expected results and impacts:

- Improve communication skills.
- greater self-acceptance and self-esteem.
- improves mental health over the long term.

Location- Via Giovanni Bovio, 6, Milan, Italy

UniSono - Rave 4 all- In Milan, as in many cities, there are many kids with Down Syndrome who would like to "party" like and with all their peers. However, this possibility is often precluded due to the lack of acceptance as active and engaging members by peers and the promoters themselves. Therefore, this project aims to create inclusive clubbing events structured to allow everyone to participate, for real: so that everyone can share one of the simplest and most exciting experiences like that of dancing together.

Expected results and impacts:

- Promote social inclusion of young people.
- Develop interpersonal relationships.
- Improve mental health.

6.1.6 Other Interventions

These groups of interventions doesn't specifically focus on any age groups. interventions aimed at promoting art and culture in the community. These interventions include community theaters, public art installations, and other creative initiatives designed to engage residents and promote a sense of community pride. Additionally, zero-impact audio services are being implemented in neighborhoods, reducing noise pollution while still providing access to cultural events and entertainment. By promoting art and culture, these interventions can inspire creativity and foster a sense of community identity among people. Community theaters and other creative initiatives can provide opportunities for people to express themselves and develop their artistic talents, while also promoting social inclusion and building connections with other residents. Additionally, the zero-

impact audio services can provide a safe and enjoyable environment for young people to socialize and participate in cultural events, without the negative impacts of noise pollution.

Kafka of Suburbia – reloaded- will engage the people of Affori through open workshops and installations using the Social Community Theater methodology, which will later be displayed in the famous Sala Shakespeare of the Teatro Elfo Puccini.

Expected results and impacts:

- Promote culture and art.
- Promoting Creativity for Youth.
- Strengthen social cohesion.

Location- Affori

Solar Vibes Cargo Flotta- The project's main goal is to increase active citizenship and the role of the third sector through environmentally conscious action, hence promoting neighborhood well-being. they developed pedal-assisted cargo bikes equipped with an audio system for the management of small proximity events. The cargo bikes will be shared with the network of associations active in the areas to facilitate the promotion of social initiatives in parks, squares, and condominium courtyards. The cargo fleet aims to provide a simple zero-impact audio service. Not only the third sector, but cargo bikes can also support the organization of birthday parties, small neighborhood shops, and schools.

Expected results and impacts:

- Promote social cohesion.
- Zero negative impact on the environment.

Location- Isola, Cascina Bellaria, Bisceglie, Vigentino-Fatima

The following table presents a comprehensive summary of the percentage of interventions aimed at different stakeholders. As we can observe, the vast majority of the interventions are directed toward addressing the needs of all residents, teenagers, and children. It is also worth noting that some interventions made as part of the 15-minute

city policy are targeted at the most vulnerable groups of the population, such as, the disabled, families experiencing hardship, women victims, etc.

% distribution of 'Interventions focused on '

Interventions focused on	Count of Interventions focused on
All residents	22.22%
Children	16.67%
Teenagers	16.67%
Poor Families	5.56%
Art & culture	5.56%
Poor Families & People with disabilities	5.56%
Women victims	5.56%
Children & young people	5.56%
Young People	5.56%
Environment	5.56%
People with disabilities	5.56%
(blank)	0.00%
Grand Total	100.00%

Table 4: Distribution of interventions focused on different stakeholders.

6.2 Vulnerable neighborhoods:

Barona	Trenno
Quarto Oggiaro	Gallaratese
Gratosoglio – Ticinello	Villapizzone
San Siro	Lorenteggio
Baggio	Comasina

Parco Lambro – Cimiano	QT 8
Ortomercato	Villapizzone
Farini	Selinunte
Navigli	P. Monlué - Ponte Lambro
Niguarda	Ortomercato
Giambellino	Dergano
Garibaldi	Scalo Romana
Città Studi	Corvetto-lodi
Bovisa	Via Padova

Based on a number of factors listed in the methodology chapter, the following areas were chosen as being particularly vulnerable and in need of attention:

6.3 Mapping of Vulnerable neighborhoods and interventions:

In the previous chapter, a number of factors that were used to identify vulnerable neighborhoods in Milan were discussed. These neighborhoods have now been pinned on a map, which also includes the zones of each municipality in Milan.

Then, all of the municipality's interventions in different neighborhoods were pinned to the same map. At first look, this would provide us with information on whether they are

putting into practice the neighborhood improvement strategies that genuinely demand immediate attention.

Figure 20: Mapping of vulnerable neighborhoods and interventions

6.4 Characteristics of the neighborhood vs type of intervention:

From the above map, we can observe that interventions are being implemented in various neighborhoods, but if we examine the features of the neighborhood and the sort of intervention in that region, we can see a mismatch between the needs and the problems. For instance, in Via Appennini, 50, the neighborhood with the highest dependency index and the majority of residents who are 65 years and older receives a child-focused

intervention called 'iGame al Galla' which is a hub for young students to learn and interact. Similarly, the Barona district has a high dependence rate. Yet, a child-focused intervention was implemented. Youth learning initiatives have also been implemented in some neighborhoods. However, those activities will be far more beneficial in neighborhoods with a high percentage of school dropouts.

In many neighborhoods, it is evident that there is a significant elderly population, but we can observe that in a few neighborhoods, there is a noticeable lack of home delivery options and pharmacies to meet their needs. It is concerning that despite this, interventions implemented in these neighborhoods tend to focus on other issues that do not directly address the needs of the elderly population. As a result, it is evident that these initiatives are not adequately tailored to the needs of the people living in the neighborhood and are unable to solve the issues that require immediate attention. This lack of attention to the needs of the elderly population can lead to further isolation and neglect, which can have severe consequences for their health and well-being. It is therefore crucial that neighborhood interventions are designed to address the specific needs of the community and take into account the unique challenges faced by different age groups. By doing so, we can create a more inclusive and supportive community that promotes the health and well-being of all its members, regardless of age or background. Moreover, on the positive side, it can be recognized that almost all neighborhoods face the challenge of the presence of unhealthy production activities that contribute to air pollution. It is crucial to note that these activities can have a significant impact on the environment and human health. Therefore, it is encouraging to see that initiatives such as the Open Squares and Open Streets programs are being implemented in many neighborhoods to combat air pollution issues. These programs aim to reduce the usage of cars and encourage people to walk, cycle, or use public transportation instead. By doing so, it can significantly reduce CO2 emissions and, thus, help tackle the air pollution problem.

6.5 Vulnerable neighborhoods with no interventions:

As we can see on the map, not all of the vulnerable neighborhoods receive the necessary intervention and support they require, resulting in an inequitable distribution of intervention across the city. Some vulnerable neighborhoods have a few interventions

nearby, while others have none. It is crucial to recognize these disparities and address them to ensure that every neighborhood in Milan receives the resources and assistance they need. Below is a list of vulnerable neighborhoods and the number of interventions available nearby.

Total 'Number of Interventions' by 'Vulnerable Neighborhoods'

Vulnerable neighborhoods	The sum of the Number of Interventions
Ortomercato	3
Corvetto-lodi	2
Barona	2
Niguarda	2
Baggio	1
Selinunte	1
Gallaratese	1
Dergano	1
Farini	1
Giambellino	1
P. Monlué - Ponte Lambro	0
San Siro	0
QT 8	0
Citta Studi	0
Garibaldi	0
Via Padova	0
Parco Lambro – Cimiano	0
Comasina	0
Quarto Oggiaro	0
Navigli	0
Scalo Romana	0
Bovisa	0
Trenno	0
Gratosoglio – Ticinello	0
Villapizzone	0
Lorenteggio	0
Mecenate	0

Table 5: Number of interventions in vulnerable neighborhoods

By examining the specific risk factors present in these vulnerable neighborhoods, we can gain a deeper insight into the unique challenges faced by residents and develop targeted interventions to address their needs. This detailed analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the complex issues facing vulnerable communities and allows policymakers to develop targeted interventions that can help improve outcomes for residents. By prioritizing neighborhoods based on their level of vulnerability, we can ensure that resources are allocated where they are needed most. Because as we can see from the list below vulnerable neighborhoods like Comasina and Quarto Oggario, which have been identified as having more than three risk indicators, such as a high crime rate, a high unemployment rate, a high incidence of school dropouts, etc., do not receive any intervention.

- **Comasina**- high dropout rate, High number of students without a diploma, high number of immigrants, high unemployment rate.
- **Quarto Oggario**- high crime rate, high dropout rates, High number of students without a diploma, high unemployment rate.
- **Villapizzone**- high dropout rate, High number of students without a diploma, high number of immigrants.
- **Bovisa**- high number of 65+ age population living alone, high dropout rates, high number of immigrants.
- **P. Monlué - Ponte Lambro**- High number of students without a diploma, high number of immigrants, high unemployment rate.
- **Città studi**- high number of 85+ population, high number of 65+ age population living alone.
- **Trenno**- high unemployment rate, high dropout rate.
- **Via Padova**- high dropout rate, high number of immigrants.
- **Mecenate**- High dependence index, less participation in the labor market.

- **Scalo romana**- High number of students without a diploma, high unemployment rate.
- **Lorenteggio**- High dependency rate, high crime rate
- **Gratosoglio**- High dependence index, high unemployment rate.
- **QT 8**- High dependency rate.
- **San siro**- high crime rate.
- **Parco Lambro – Cimiano**- High dependency rate.
- **Navigli**- high number of 65+ age population living alone.
- **Garibaldi**- high number of 65+ age population living alone.

The implementation of the 15-minute city policy in Milan is more in line with the bottom-up approach, with the municipality publishing a call and citizens proposing projects that are capable of generating a positive social impact in the neighborhoods. According to the literature, the main objective of the 15-minute city is to ensure that everyone has access to basic necessities like living, working, commerce, healthcare, education, and entertainment in less than 15 minutes and that the quality of these amenities is high throughout all neighborhoods to prevent inequality. However, if we examine how the policy is put into practice in Milan and the chosen projects to implement in neighborhoods in order to achieve the 15-minute city, we can see that the policy's characteristics in Milan differ from those described in the literature. For instance, not every intervention in the neighborhood may be referred to as an essential amenity like healthcare, education, etc. But the interventions' ultimate objective is to have a positive social impact in the neighborhood and in the long run to aid in the development of 15-minute neighborhoods by making the neighborhoods self-sufficient.

Although the interventions proposed by citizens are capable of generating a positive social impact in those neighborhoods, there may be some problems with the way the strategy is being carried out in Milan. With the existing system of the municipality posting a call and the citizens coming up with a project in the neighborhoods, it's possible that certain neighborhoods won't get any interventions if the residents there lack awareness and don't know how to put forward a solution for their neighborhood. Moreover, not all demographic groups are being targeted by neighborhood interventions; for example, while there are many interventions in the neighborhoods

focusing on young people, there are none for the elderly, despite the fact that they make up the majority of residents in those neighborhoods.

Lack of awareness by locals in some neighborhoods may also account for the absence of intervention in some neighborhoods. For instance, neighborhoods like *quarto Orzagio*, *ponte Lambro*, where immigrants make up the majority of the population don't have any intervention. Similar to this, no interventions have been recommended in numerous neighborhoods where the majority of residents lack a diploma and are school dropouts. It's possible that the locals in certain neighborhoods lack the knowledge necessary to put forward a project that would benefit them. Residents of vulnerable neighborhoods may not have been aware of the policy, which would explain why they did not participate. Even if they were aware, however, language barriers, paperwork hurdles, and a lack of contacts may have prevented them from contributing to the policy and suggesting projects.

One of the major issues raised by experts in relation to the 15-minute city policy is that it will widen the gap between the rich and the poor by only providing access to amenities for those living in the city center within 15 minutes while leaving those in the outlying districts behind. But if we examine how the policy is put into practice in Milan, we can see that the key approach handled by the Milan Municipality while implementing the policy is the development of initiatives in all zones of Milan except zone 1 (where the wealthy neighborhoods exist). This strategy is used to prevent both spatial inequality and the gap between the rich and the poor. So, in the context of Milan, the likelihood that the policy will increase the gap between the rich and the poor and worsen geographical inequalities is quite low.

The city of Milan is implementing the policy in a different approach from what we have previously seen in the literature analysis on the 15-minute city strategy concept and its primary pillars. One of the pillars of the 15-minute city, as evidenced by the literature evaluation, is diversity, and the literature review also highlights the importance of diversified cultural development in neighborhoods. Nonetheless, the top priority in Milan is to support local businesses and promote neighborhood self-sufficiency. A focus on diversity or programs to promote immigrant integration is not part of Milan's "15-minute city" agenda but rather aims to benefit all residents by promoting a more

accessible and equitable urban environment. However, it's worth noting that the 15-minute city policy could potentially benefit immigrant communities, who may face greater social isolation due to factors such as language barriers, and lack of familiarity with the neighborhood. By creating 15-minute walkable neighborhoods social capital in the neighborhoods increase and therefore it could help immigrants feel more connected to their neighborhoods and reduce feelings of isolation.

Milan has put a great emphasis on addressing the needs of vulnerable populations like disabled individuals and families living in the fragility while implementing the 15-minute city policy. For example, Milan has introduced a number of programs to help underprivileged groups to have better access to food. This includes developing programs that offer complete, nutritionally balanced meals to support families and people who are vulnerable or at risk of social exclusion. Also, programs to improve access to mental health support and services for children and young people to regain their confidence and overcome fear. Additionally, Milan has improved disabled people's access to sporting possibilities. This includes the development of gyms and training facilities for fencing, as well as assistance programs for persons with disabilities that provide employment opportunities in restaurants.

Although Milan has done a remarkable effort of prioritizing vulnerable groups like the disabled and low-income families, it is important to note that some neighborhoods have a majority of elderly residents, yet there aren't any initiatives specifically designed to meet their needs. It is crucial to understand the particular difficulties that the aged population faces and to take proactive steps to ensure their well-being. To build a more inclusive and equitable neighborhood, the city must constantly assess and improve its programs to cater to the needs of all vulnerable populations, including the elderly.

To sum up, Milan's emphasis on vulnerable populations in its implementation of the 15-minute city policy is a key factor in creating a more equitable and inclusive city. By ensuring that essential services and amenities are easily accessible to all citizens, regardless of income or social status, Milan is working to create a more livable and sustainable urban environment for everyone.

7 Conclusion

The thesis aimed to explore the relationship between the 15-minute city policy and social inclusion in Milan, Italy. Through a comprehensive analysis of relevant literature and a case study of Milan's 15-minute city policy, this thesis has drawn the following conclusions:

Firstly, the 15-minute city policy has the potential to enhance social inclusion by creating more accessible and equitable urban environments. The policy promotes walkability, cycling, and public transportation, which can reduce transportation costs and significantly lower CO₂ emissions. Also, the policy can enhance and promote local businesses while increasing access to services, employment prospects, and educational possibilities for marginalized neighborhoods.

Secondly, Milan's 15-minute city policy has demonstrated several positive outcomes in terms of social inclusion. The policy has improved accessibility to essential services, such as healthcare and education, and created more green spaces and public areas for communities to gather and interact. Milan has taken remarkable steps to promote social inclusion and accessibility to services within 15 minutes. In order to implement the policy, Milan adopts a bottom-up strategy. For example, the municipality publishes a call, and the citizens respond with project ideas for the neighborhoods. The bottom-up approach of involving the community in proposing projects has the potential to foster a sense of ownership and participation. However, there is a risk of leaving behind certain neighborhoods, particularly those neighborhoods where the majority of residents are immigrants or where many people do not have a high school education because of language and other barriers or lack of awareness to responding to a call. To ensure that

no one is left behind, Milan should consider all neighborhoods and explore alternative approaches to engage marginalized communities in the policy-making process. The success of the initiative ultimately depends on the city's ability to address the needs of all its residents, regardless of their background or circumstances. Therefore, Milan must take a more inclusive approach to ensure that the benefits of the policy are equally distributed and accessible to all. The success of the 15-minute city policy in promoting social inclusion depends on effective community engagement and participation. The policy must be implemented in a way that considers the diverse needs and preferences of different communities to ensure that all residents benefit from the policy.

Furthermore, in literature, the 15-minute city urban policy has been found to have several drawbacks that may lead to increased inequality within cities. However, the case of Milan provides a strategy to address this issue. By implementing the 15-minute city initiatives in all neighborhoods except for zone 1, Milan has been able to ensure that the benefits of this policy are accessible to all residents, rather than only those in the city center. This approach may serve as a valuable model for other cities seeking to implement the 15-minute city policy in a way that promotes equity and reduces disparities.

Overall, this thesis has shown that the 15-minute city policy has the potential to enhance social inclusion in urban environments. However, to ensure its success, policymakers must consider the unique needs and preferences of different communities and engage them in the policy-making process.

7.1 Limitations

Lack of Primary Data: The report is solely based on secondary sources found online, news, and documents published on the municipality website. No primary data was taken to know the needs of the people and understand the problems better in the neighborhoods. This limitation could have affected the accuracy of the findings and conclusions.

Reliance on Outdated Data: The data used to identify vulnerable neighborhoods in the report was taken from the report published in 2011. The census is conducted once every ten years, and the data for 2021 that was broken down to the neighborhood level was not yet published. Therefore, the accuracy of the results may not be very high.

Incomplete Data: While the report makes use of available data sources, there may be additional factors or information that were not captured by these sources, which could have affected the findings. For instance, additional interventions that are a part of the 15-minute city policy were recently published on the municipality website, but because complete details about the interventions and their locations couldn't be located, they weren't taken into consideration in this thesis due to time constraints. As a result, the findings and conclusions presented in this thesis may not fully reflect the current state of interventions in the neighborhoods analyzed. It is important to note that the exclusion of these interventions could potentially affect the accuracy and completeness of the results. Therefore, future research should take into account these additional interventions to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the interventions carried out by the municipality in these neighborhoods.

Limited Scope: The report's scope is limited to the information available online and in municipality documents. Other relevant information outside of these sources may have been missed. therefore, these limitations should be taken into account when interpreting the findings and conclusions of the report, and further research is needed to obtain a more complete and accurate understanding of the neighborhood's needs and problems.

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9 Appendix

Table 6: Demographics and other data of neighborhoods where the project is being implemented

Neighborhoods

Demographics

	Depende nce Index	Average age Inndex	Percentag e of young people adults 15- 34	Percentage of foreigners	Unhealth y producti on activities	Service s for foreign ers	Numb er of librari es
Via Martiri Oscuri	40.8	43.4	24.2	34.3	yes	Yes	0
Isola district	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	0
Via Toce	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	0
Porta Venezia- Lazzaretto district	53.5	45.9	21.3	12.3	yes	Yes	1
Via Rovereto	40.8	43.4	24.2	34.3	yes	Yes	1
Corvetto Milano	55.8	45.7	20.8	26.7	yes	Yes	1
Municipio 7	58.8	46.1	20	19.5	yes	Yes	1
Barona district	75.3	49.4	19.8	15.7	yes	Yes	0
Via Appennini, 50	76.4	50.6	17.5	12.5	yes	Yes	0
Cascina Merlata	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	0
San Cristoforo	75.3	49.4	19.8	15.7	yes	Yes	1
Forlanini	54.7	45.5	20.8	19.8	yes	Yes	0
Taliedo	54.7	45.5	20.8	19.8	yes	Yes	0
Morsenchio	54.7	45.5	20.8	19.8	yes	Yes	0
Salomone districts	54.7	45.5	20.8	19.8	yes	Yes	0
Via Filippo Sasseti 2	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	0
Affori	49.7	43.7	21.5	30	yes	Yes	1
Via Giovanni Bovio, 6	44	42.6	23.5	34.6	yes	Yes	1
Cascina Bellaria	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	1
Bisceglie	46.4	44.7	21.9	19.2	yes	Yes	1
Vigentino- Fatima					yes	Yes	1
Dergano	44	42.6	23.5	34.6	yes	Yes	1
Parco Nord Milano	63.2	47.7	19.5	15.7	yes	Yes	1

Neighborhoods

	Number of schools:	Presence of childcare services:	Presence of shops with home delivery options
Via Martiri Oscuri	2	yes	Few
Isola district	2	yes	Yes
Via Toce	2	yes	Yes
Porta Venezia-Lazzaretto district	5	few	Yes
Via Rovereto	2	yes	Few
Corvetto	4	yes	Yes
Milano Municipio 7	34	yes	Yes
Barona district	6	yes	Yes
Via Appennini, 50	3	yes	Few
Cascina Merlata	1	few	Few
San Cristoforo	2	few	Yes
Forlanini	3	few	Yes
Taliedo	2	few	Yes
Morsenchio	1	few	Yes
Salomone districts	1	few	Yes
Via Filippo Sassetti 2	1	yes	Yes
Affori	4	yes	Few
Via Giovanni Bovio, 6	1	few	yes
Cascina Bellaria	4	yes	Few
Bisceglie	5	yes	Few
Vigentino-Fatima	4	few	Few
Dergano	3	few	Yes
Parco Nord Milano	4	yes	Yes

Table 7: List of all interventions that are part of the 15-minute city policy and their aim and locations.

List of projects	Aim	Location
Strade Aperte	To encourage walking and cycling	"Via Martiri Oscuri", Isola district, Via Toce, Porta Venezia-Lazzaretto district, Isola district, Via Minniti.
Città 30	Implement 30 km/h speed limit in residential zones with around 60% of the entire urban road network.	Via Rovereto
Piazze Aperte	To transform public space into a meeting and socializing place.	In all municipio zones

Adotta una gallina	To get eggs directly from the farm using a regenerative micro supply chain.	Corvetto 4, Vigentino 5 and Chiaravalle 5
Coach di quartiere 2023	to bring sports closer to kids who cannot physically or financially afford traditional sports by relocating closed gyms into open spaces with free admission.	Milano Municipio 7
Il Parlamento dei bambini	To organize a free, two-week summer camp for children aged 6 to 10. The Children's Parliament is a theatre workshop where youngsters may express their thoughts about the world. by writing and by acting out in front of the public. Children are to be taught about their rights and the societal concerns that affect them	Barona district 6
iGame al Galla	to develop a hub that serves as a hub for young people to interact, have fun, learn, express themselves, and collaborate.	Via Appennini, 50, (8)

Mare food academy	to establish a training and job placement program for motivated young people in economically and socially precarious situations, giving them the chance to master a trade in the restaurant industry and rethink their future.	San Siro (7), Cascina Merlata (8), San Cristoforo (7), Rogoredo(4), Santa Giulia (4)
Pasto Sospeso - A Milano l'inclusione sa di buono	to support families and individuals with fragility or at risk of social exclusion and provide complete and nutritionally balanced meals aims to help improve the living conditions of many people and families in difficulty. At the same time providing industrious opportunities to categories of fragile citizens, young people with disabilities, and opportunities for conviviality and social cohesion. it also intends to promote food education and a healthy lifestyle	Forlanini (4) Taliedo (4), Morsenchio (4), Forlanini 4, and Salomone districts
La scherma per il benessere del corpo e della mente	To provide fencing lessons at Accademia Scherma Milano, including those who are sighted, blind, or have other physical or mental disabilities, in a newly rebuilt gym with no physical obstacles.	Via Filippo Sasseti 2

Kafka of Suburbia – reloaded	to engage the people of Affori through open workshops and installations using the Social Community Theater methodology, which will later be displayed in the famous Sala Shakespeare of the Teatro Elfo Puccini.	Affori 9
MEM-Out, per un'educazione della memoria in uscita	The proposal intends to launch a brand-new method of interaction between the public and the institution, in which the Memorial, from a place of welcome, becomes an active agent that encounters the territory, leaving its spaces. It aims to provide a widely accessible service for engaging and developing the stories that this location both preserves and communicates.	Milano Centrale
Radio Dynamo Milano	it aims to implement Recreational Therapy projects for children and young people with disabilities and chronic diseases to regain self-confidence, overcome their fears, learn to listen to each other, and process their emotions. it involves children and teenagers in the creation of small radio programs during the sessions. Dynamo guests have fun drafting texts on topics proposed by the staff and broadcast live or record the radio formats that they themselves have prepared.	Via Giovanni Bovio, 6, Milan, Italy

Solar Vibes Cargo Flotta	The project's main goal is to increase active citizenship and the role of the third sector through environmentally conscious action, hence promoting neighbourhood well-being. they developed pedal assisted cargo bikes equipped with an audio system for the management of small proximity events. The cargo bikes, will be shared with the network of associations active in the areas to facilitate the promotion of social initiatives in parks, squares and condominium courtyards. The cargo fleet aims to provide a simple zero impact audio service. Not only the third sector, cargo bikes can support the organization of birthday parties, small neighborhood shops, schools .	Isola, Cascina Bellaria 7, Bisceglie, Vigentino- Fatima
UniSono - Rave 4 all	In Milan, as in many cities, there are many kids with Down Syndrome who would like to "party" like and with all their peers. However, this possibility is often precluded due to the lack of acceptance as active and engaging members by peers and the promoters themselves. therefore this project aims to create inclusive clubbing events structured to allow everyone to participate, for real: so that everyone can share one of the simplest and most exciting experiences like that of dancing together.	
La sartoria che cura	To offer free services include tailoring classes and a psychological support desk for wome who have been the victims of abuse and violence.	Dergano 9
MI Barrio's	It aims to accompany teenagers in harmonious growth through art and culture and enhance the neighborhood and its meeting place by hosting various cultural events.	Barona district 6

<p>Campus creativo e naturalistico Corvetto</p>	<p>it intends to offer a service with 8-hour activities a day for 30 children of the neighborhood, aged between 6 and 11. They will be creative activities with artists with proven educational experience, naturalistic activities in the Agroforest and guided visits to local museums followed by workshops with the word. It will be A unique experience as it combines a family assistance service with creative and educational activities</p>	<p>Corvetto district</p>
<p>Bookstop – Panchine letterarie</p>	<p>it aims to create literary benches in bookstop where you can meet to read, borrow, buy, discuss books, the bookstop also tells you the story of the area and the encounter between nature and the city who advises you on what to do on the weekend also its a bench where you can find stories: meetings with the author, workshops, cultural events for all ages.</p>	<p>borders of Parco Nord Milano. 9</p>

List of all interventions that are part of the 15-minute city policy and the existing problems in the neighborhood where the interventions are being implemented:

<p>List of projects</p>	<p>Existing problems in the neighborhood</p>

Strade Aperte	<p>Via Martiri Oscuri-</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. No libraries 3. Few shops with home delivery options <p>Isola, Via toce, Via Minniti.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No libraries 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. <p>Porta Venezia</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. few childcare services 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance
Città 30	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. the presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. No libraries 3. Few shops with home delivery options
Piazze Aperte	
Adotta una gallina	<p>Corvetto-</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 2. No Kindergartens (public) <p>Vigentino</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 2. Few childcare services. 3. No libraries 4. Few shops with home delivery options <p>Chiaravalle</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Few childcare services 2. No libraries 3. Few public schools 4. few shops with home delivery options.

Coach di quartiere 2023	High dependence rate
Il Parlamento dei bambini	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High dependence rate 2. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 3. No libraries 4. Few pharmacies 5. High unemployment rate
iGame al Galla	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High dependence rate 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 3. no libraries 4. few shops with home delivery options.
Mare food academy	<p>San siro</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High dependence rate 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 3. High crime rate <p>Cascina Merlata</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. Few childcare services 3. No libraries 4. Few shops with home delivery options <p>San Cristoforo</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. Few childcare services. <p>Rogoredo, Santa Giulia</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. No libraries 3. Few shops with home delivery options

<p>Pasto Sospeso - A Milano l'inclusione sa di buono</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Few childcare services 2. No libraries 3. No Kindergartens (public) 4. few pharmacies
<p>La scherma per il benessere del corpo e della mente</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No libraries 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance.
<p>Kafka of Suburbia – reloaded</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. 2. Few shops with home delivery options
<p>MEM-Out, per un'educazione della memoria in uscita</p>	<p>presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance.</p>

Radio Dynamo Milano	Few childcare services.
Solar Vibes Cargo Flotta	<p>Isola</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No libraries 2. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance. <p>Via Cascina Bellaria</p> <p>Few shops with home delivery options</p> <p>Bisceglie</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No Kindergartens (public) 2. Few shops with home delivery options <p>Vigentino</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 2. Few childcare services. 3. No libraries 4. Few shops with home delivery options
UniSono - Rave 4 all	
La sartoria che cura	Few childcare services.

MI Barrio's	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High dependence rate 2. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 3. No libraries 4. Few pharmacies 5. High unemployment rate
Campus creativo e naturalistico Corvetto	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High number of unhealthy production activities with significant environmental relevance. 2. No Kindergartens (public)
Bookstop – Panchine letterarie	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. presence of unhealthy production activity with significant environmental relevance

List of Vulnerable neighborhoods.

- High Dependency rate (Censimento Milano, 2011)

- Population over 65 who live alone (Censimento Milano, 2011)

- Unemployment rate (Censimento Milano, 2011)

- Neighborhoods with the most immigrants (Censimento Milano, 2011)

- Neighborhoods with the highest school dropouts (Censimento Milano, 2011)

- Neighborhoods with students who don't have a diploma (Censimento Milano, 2011)

High crime rate:

- Quarto Oggiaro
- Barona
- corvette
- Via Padua
- San Siro
- Lorenteggio